

MASTER THESIS
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How do different ventilation strategies perform from a holistic sustainability perspective in the context of Nordic office building design?
A case study of Vertikal Nydalen

ABSTRACT

Ventilation has a significant impact on the performance of office buildings. It affects energy consumption, material requirements, indoor environmental quality, interior design, capital costs and long-term operation. This is particularly important in Nordic climates. Cold winters increase heat loss and can lead to discomfort, whilst milder summers allow the use of outdoor air for passive cooling. Previous studies have addressed energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, indoor climate and costs, but often in isolation from one another. However, there are few studies that compare natural, hybrid and mechanical ventilation using a common sustainability framework. This work fills this gap by comparing these three ventilation strategies from environmental, social and economic perspectives.

Vertikal Nydalen, also known as Gullhaug Torg 2A, in Oslo was chosen as the case study. The office areas use a realised natural ventilation system in a cold urban climate. This solution was compared with two hypothetical alternatives for the same representative office area. A hybrid ventilation system and a mechanical ventilation system was chosen for that. The hybrid scenario combines natural ventilation with mechanical support, while the mechanical scenario is based on demand-controlled supply and extract air. The assessment includes nine indicators across three sustainability dimensions. Environmental performance was assessed through primary energy demand, greenhouse gas emissions and ecopoints. Social performance was assessed through user comfort, design aspects and daylight conditions. Economic performance was assessed through investment costs, maintenance costs and energy costs. The analysis used measured operational data, previous simulation results, life-cycle assessment data, project documents, literature, cost benchmarks and defined assumptions. The results were then translated into a five-point rating system to make the different indicators easier to compare.

The results show that natural ventilation performed best across all evaluated criteria. Due to the low energy consumption during operation and the emissions associated with the materials used, this resulted in the lowest values in the life cycle and cost analysis. It also performed well socially because the system supported high ceiling heights, reduced visible technical installations and received positive user feedback. Hybrid ventilation performed as an intermediate solution. It required more technical equipment what caused more embodied emissions and higher costs. At the same time it also needs more space because of the ducts which are often covered with a suspended ceiling. Mechanical ventilation received the lowest overall score in all of the criteria.

However, the results do not mean that mechanical ventilation is generally an unsuitable solution. The best ventilation strategy depends on the project, the climate, the building design and the performance priorities. Natural ventilation can be a strong sustainability strategy if it is well integrated into the architecture, the façade design and the control system. Hybrid ventilation can be useful when natural ventilation alone is insufficient and more stable indoor air quality is required. Mechanical ventilation remains important when a stable airflow, filtration, sound insulation or strict indoor climate requirements are necessary. Mechanical systems are particularly well suited to ensuring indoor air quality in areas affected by noise and air pollution. Further research should compare measurement data from completed buildings with natural, hybrid and mechanical ventilation to provide a more solid basis for a holistic assessment in Nordic climates.

SAMMENDRAG

Ventilasjon har stor betydning for kontorbyggs ytelse. Det påvirker energiforbruk, materialbehov, inneklima, interiørdesign, investeringskostnader og drift på lang sikt. Dette er særlig viktig i nordiske klima. Kalde vintre øker varmetapet og kan føre til ubehag, mens mildere somre gjør det mulig å bruke uteluft til passiv kjøling. Tidligere studier har sett på energiforbruk, klimagassutslipp, inneklima og kostnader, men ofte isolert fra hverandre. Det finnes imidlertid få studier som sammenligner naturlig, hybrid og mekanisk ventilasjon ved hjelp av et felles bærekraftsrammeverk. Dette arbeidet fyller dette tomrommet ved å sammenligne disse tre ventilasjonsstrategiene fra miljømessige, sosiale og økonomiske perspektiver.

Vertikal Nydalen, også kjent som Gullhaug Torg 2A, i Oslo ble valgt som case-studie. Kontorarealene benytter et realisert naturlig ventilasjonssystem i et kaldt byklima. Denne løsningen ble sammenlignet med to hypotetiske alternativer for det samme representative kontorarealet. Et hybridventilasjonssystem og et mekanisk ventilasjonssystem ble valgt for dette. Hybridscenariet kombinerer naturlig ventilasjon med mekanisk støtte, mens det mekaniske scenariet er basert på behovsstyrt tilluft og avtrekk. Vurderingen omfatter ni indikatorer fordelt på tre bærekraftsdimensjoner. Miljøprestasjon ble vurdert gjennom primærenergibehov, klimagassutslipp og økopoeng. Sosial ytelse ble vurdert gjennom brukerkomfort, designaspekter og dagslysforhold. Økonomisk ytelse ble vurdert gjennom investeringskostnader, vedlikeholdskostnader og energikostnader. Analysen benyttet målte driftsdata, tidligere simuleringsresultater, livssyklusvurderingsdata, prosjektdokumenter, litteratur, kostnadsreferanser og definerte forutsetninger. Resultatene ble deretter omregnet til et femtrinns vurderingssystem for å gjøre de ulike indikatorene lettere å sammenligne.

Resultatene viser at naturlig ventilasjon presterte best på tvers av alle evaluerte kriterier. På grunn av det lave energiforbruket under drift og utslippene knyttet til materialene som ble brukt, resulterte dette i de laveste verdiene i livssyklus- og kostnadsanalysen. Den presterte også godt sosialt fordi systemet støttet høye takhøyder, reduserte synlige tekniske installasjoner og fikk positive tilbakemeldinger fra brukerne. Hybridventilasjon presterte som en mellomløsning. Den krevde mer teknisk utstyr, noe som førte til flere innebygde utslipp og høyere kostnader. Samtidig krever den også mer plass på grunn av kanalene, som ofte dekkes av et undertak. Mekanisk ventilasjon fikk den laveste samlede poengsummen på alle kriteriene.

Resultatene betyr imidlertid ikke at mekanisk ventilasjon generelt er en uegnet løsning. Den beste ventilasjonsstrategien avhenger av prosjektet, klimaet, bygningens utforming og ytelsesprioriteringene. Naturlig ventilasjon kan være en sterk bærekraftsstrategi hvis den er godt integrert i arkitekturen, fasadedesignet og reguleringssystemet. Hybridventilasjon kan være nyttig når naturlig ventilasjon alene ikke er tilstrekkelig og det kreves en mer stabil inneklima. Mekanisk ventilasjon er fortsatt viktig når det er behov for stabil luftstrøm, filtrering, lydisolering eller strenge krav til inneklima. Mekaniske systemer er spesielt godt egnet til å sikre inneklima i områder som er utsatt for støy og luftforurensning. Videre forskning bør sammenligne måledata fra ferdigstilte bygninger med naturlig, hybrid og mekanisk ventilasjon for å gi et mer solid grunnlag for en helhetlig vurdering i nordiske klima.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AHU	Air-Handling Unit
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
CAV	Constant Air Volume
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DCV	Demand-Controlled Ventilation
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GT2A	Gullhaug Torg 2A
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IAQ	Indoor Air Quality
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
PPD	Predicted Percentage Dissatisfied
VAV	Variable Air Volume
ZEB	Zero Emission Buildings

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1 INTRODUCTION

Ventilation is a central element of office building performance because it affects energy use, material demand, indoor environmental quality, spatial design and long-term operation. In Nordic climates, this role is particularly important. Low winter temperatures increase the risk of ventilation related heat loss and cold period discomfort while moderate summer conditions can support passive cooling through outdoor air. The choice of ventilation strategy therefore influences technical performance but also the overall sustainability impact of a building.

This study evaluates the sustainability performance through a case study of Vertikal Nydalen, also referred to as Gullhaug Torg 2A (GT2A). The building is relevant because its office spaces were designed around a natural ventilation (NV) concept rather than a conventional fully mechanical system. The project therefore provides a practical basis for studying whether NV principles can contribute to sustainable office design in a Nordic context. The thesis compares the as-built NV scenario with hypothetical hybrid ventilation (HV) and mechanical ventilation (MV) alternatives. The comparison is structured around environmental, social and economic sustainability criteria in order to assess the consequences of ventilation strategy beyond energy performance alone.

1.1 CONTEXT

Ventilation in office buildings affects more than the technical aspects of supplying and extracting air. Ventilation systems influence energy use, material demand, indoor environmental quality, spatial design, and construction and operating costs. They affect operational energy through heating, cooling and fan electricity, while also contributing to embodied impacts through ducts, air-handling units (AHU), controls, sensors and replacements. Fong et al. (2017) show that ventilation methods can lead to different environmental and economic outcomes when life cycle assessment (LCA) and life cycle costing (LCC) are considered together. Kiamili et al. (2020) demonstrate that heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems can represent a substantial share of embodied carbon in office buildings. Rabani et al. (2025) quantify greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from NV, HV and MV strategies, showing the relevance of comparing HVAC solutions across operational and material related emissions.

These issues are especially relevant in Nordic climates, where ventilation must respond to long heating seasons, low outdoor temperatures, strong seasonal variation and dry outdoor air. Supplying sufficient fresh air in winter can increase heating demand and create risks of draught or low indoor temperatures if the air is not properly tempered. Laverge and Janssens (2012) show that heat recovery ventilation must be evaluated in relation to primary energy use, climate conditions and system efficiency. Office buildings must provide acceptable thermal comfort, air quality and user satisfaction, and the ventilation strategy plays a central role in these aspects. Justo Alonso et al. (2024) show that humidity, carbon dioxide (CO₂), temperature particulate matter and are highly relevant for indoor air quality (IAQ). However, Torriani et al. (2025) further emphasise that perceived air quality is influenced by more than CO₂ concentration alone but also by personal control, user habits and office layout.

NV has gained renewed attention as an alternative to highly technical systems, but its application in cold climates remains challenging. It uses wind pressure and buoyancy rather than continuous fan-driven airflow, which can reduce fan energy consumption and technical infrastructure requirements. Zaniboni and Albatici (2022) describe NV as being strongly linked to building geometry, façade design and the outdoor climate. HV represents an intermediate strategy between fully natural and fully mechanical systems. Rabani and Petersen (2025) demonstrate that control strategy is essential in mixed-mode buildings because windows, mechanical systems and comfort targets must be coordinated. Vertikal Nydalen provides a relevant case study for examining these trade-offs because its office areas apply NV principles within a Nordic urban context. Bekkeli (2021) found that NV and HV can reduce delivered energy demand and GHG emissions

compared with MV, but also identified comfort risks related to draughts, low winter temperatures, elevated CO₂ levels and summer overheating. This thesis builds on that foundation by comparing NV, HV and MV across environmental, social and economic criteria within the same case study boundary.

1.2 RESEARCH GAP AND GOALS

Although current research into ventilation systems examines various sustainability criteria, it often treats them in isolation from one another. Environmental studies commonly address energy use, embodied emissions and life cycle impacts. Fong et al. (2017) compare ventilation methods through LCA and LCC, while Kiamili et al. (2020) show that HVAC systems can represent a significant share of embodied carbon in office buildings. Bergsdal et al. (2024) further improve the basis for environmental assessment by providing life cycle inventory data for ventilation components. Other studies focus on IAQ and the user experience. Justo Alonso et al. (2024) measure indicators of IAQ in a low-emission office building in Norway while Lassen et al. (2021) emphasise the importance of subjective user feedback in high-performance offices. Some studies combine several dimensions but have limitations in the context of this work. Rabani et al. (2025) compare the GHG emissions of NV, HV and MV, but mainly from an environmental perspective. Kim and de Dear (2021) investigate mixed ventilation as a strategy for energy-efficient comfort, but do not provide a case-specific comparison across environmental, social and economic indicators. The research gap therefore lies in the limited number of holistic, case-based assessments of ventilation strategies in Nordic office buildings, where energy consumption, emissions, indoor climate, design implications and costs must be considered together.

Based on this research gap this thesis aims to assess NV, HV and MV strategies from a holistic sustainability perspective within the Nordic office context. Vertikal Nydalen serves as a case study as it applies NV principles to office spaces characterised by a cold climate. The thesis builds on previous research by comparing the used NV solution with hypothetical hybrid and mechanical alternatives within the same building envelope. The aim is not only to compare energy demand or emissions but to evaluate how the three strategies perform in terms of environmental, social and economic aspects.

1.3 LIMITATIONS

The main limitation of this study is its broad sustainability approach. While the study brings together environmental, social and economic aspects within a single comparative framework, it does not go as deep as specialised studies in each field. The environmental assessment, comfort assessment, design analysis, daylight study and cost assessment are therefore used collectively to provide an overall overview of sustainability, rather than as detailed findings for each discipline. The results should be read as comparative indicators within the defined framework of the case study. They are based on the best available data, including measurement data from the existing NV scenario, earlier simulation results, LCA data, project documentation, literature, cost benchmarks and defined assumptions.

2 BACKGROUND

In the following literature review the theoretical basis for comparing ventilation strategies in Nordic office buildings is analysed. It begins by explaining the key principles of ventilation, before examining climate related challenges, sustainability assessment criteria and previous research findings on Vertikal Nydalen.

2.1 VENTILATION PRINCIPLES IN OFFICE BUILDINGS

Ventilation principles determine how outdoor air is supplied to, distributed within, and extracted from office spaces. This chapter presents NV, HV and MV as alternative strategies and highlights the differences in terms of driving force, technical complexity and controllability, as well as their significance for comfort, energy consumption and interior design.

2.1.1 NATURAL VENTILATION

NV relies on wind pressure and buoyancy rather than continuous fan power, so airflow is generated by weather and building geometry instead of mechanical plant (Zaniboni & Albatici, 2022). Figure 1 visualizes cross, stack, and atrium/solar-chimney pathways. Single-sided ventilation uses one façade for both inlet and outlet exchange, which makes it simple to integrate but strongly dependent on turbulence, opening design, and local façade exposure (Zhong et al., 2022). Cross ventilation uses pressure differences between separated openings to create a through-flow across the office zone or room. In practice, it typically requires openings on opposite façades and a clear internal airflow path (Fan et al., 2021). Stack ventilation instead exploits vertical temperature differences. Cooler air enters at low level and warmer indoor air rises to a higher outlet (Chen & Gorlé, 2022). Atria and solar chimneys strengthen that upward draft by extending the exhaust path or heating it with solar gains, which allows buoyancy-driven extraction to serve deeper plans (Maghrabie et al., 2022). In office design, NV is a spatial and façade strategy in which opening location, section height, and airflow continuity are inseparable from the architectural concept (Zaniboni & Albatici, 2022).

Figure 1 Principles of natural ventilation approaches in buildings

2.1.2 HYBRID VENTILATION

HV, often referred to as mixed-mode ventilation, combines natural ventilation with mechanical ventilation or cooling, so that passive and active airflow can be combined or overlapped as conditions change. Figure 2 illustrates natural supply with mechanical extract, mechanical supply with natural exhaust, and balanced MV supplemented by window opening for peak ventilation (Kim & de Dear, 2021). In the first arrangement, outdoor air enters through façade openings or passive inlets, while an exhaust fan secures a defined outlet path and stabilizes flow direction. In the second, air is filtered and delivered mechanically, whereas buoyancy or wind removes it through shafts, atria, or roof vents. Both systems ensure the air flow through the building without the need of a regular ducting system. In the third variant, the AHU provides the regular base ventilation with the possibility of integrating a heat recovery system. Operable windows are used for purge, free cooling, or short peak-load periods. (Peng et al., 2022). Controlling systems are crucial when it comes to coordinating windows, dampers, fans, and sensors (Peng et al., 2022).

Figure 2 Principles of hybrid ventilation approaches in buildings

2.1.3 MECHANICAL VENTILATION

MV uses fans to supply, extract, or both supply and extract air independently of wind and buoyancy, so airflow becomes a controllable building service function (Zaniboni & Albatici, 2022). The three scenarios in in Figure 3 illustrate balanced mechanical ventilation, extract-only mechanical ventilation, and mixed-mode mechanical ventilation. The first supplies and extracts air mechanically with no occupant-controlled window opening. The second extracts air mechanically while outdoor air enters through façade openings. The third combines mechanical supply and extract air with operable windows for additional user-controlled ventilation (Zhao et al., 2022). In office spaces these systems are usually built around AHU containing dampers, heating and cooling coils, supply and return fans, sensors, and a controller (Li et al., 2021). Heat recovery devices are commonly inserted between the exhaust and outdoor air flows so that outgoing air is preheating the incoming supply air (Zender-Świercz, 2021). The system can work either with constant air volume (CAV) or with demand-controlled ventilation (DCV) which controls the air flow through temperature, occupancy, or CO₂ concentration (Lu et al., 2022).

Figure 3 Principles of hybrid ventilation approaches in buildings

2.1.4 VENTILATION COMPARISON

The three ventilation scenarios represent different trade-offs between architectural integration, controllability and technical complexity. NV offers the strongest link between building form and airflow because it uses wind pressure and buoyancy instead of continuous fan operation (Zaniboni & Albatici, 2022). Its main advantages are low technical complexity, reduced duct space, lower fan electricity demand, and better preservation of ceiling height. However, because airflow depends on outdoor conditions and facade exposure, NV can be less reliable during cold, calm, or highly occupied periods (Zhong et al., 2022). This is consistent with Bekkeli (2021) who found that the NV scenario had the lowest GHG emissions, but also higher risks of draught, low winter temperatures and elevated CO₂ levels. HV is a middle solution, where natural airflow is supplemented by mechanical assistance when passive driving forces are insufficient (Kim & de Dear, 2021). It can retain many spatial and energy benefits of NV while improving winter and peak-load performance through mechanical support and heat recovery. Its main disadvantage is that performance

depends strongly on control logic, since windows, dampers, fans, and sensors must be coordinated to avoid comfort problems or unnecessary energy use (Peng et al., 2022). MV provides the most predictable indoor climate because supply and extract airflow can be controlled independently of weather conditions (Zhao et al., 2022). It also allows filtration, heat recovery, and demand-controlled operation, which can support stable IAQ in Nordic offices. Nevertheless, MV requires the most ducts, plant space, commissioning, maintenance, and embodied material input, while heat recovery benefits must be balanced against fan energy and pressure losses (Zender-Świercz, 2021).

2.2 IMPACT OF CLIMATE CONDITIONS ON VENTILATION

The local climate conditions have a significant impact on ventilation design, as outdoor temperature, humidity, and solar radiation determine how much outdoor air can be used directly and how much conditioning is required before supply to occupied spaces (Laverge & Janssens, 2012). In Nordic climates, this is especially relevant because buildings are exposed to long heating seasons, low winter temperatures, and strong seasonal differences (Alonso et al., 2015). Compared with Zurich as a central European reference, Oslo represents a colder, more heating dominated climate, while still offering moderate summer conditions that can support passive cooling.

Figure 4 Psychrometric climate chart of Oslo, Norway and Zurich, Switzerland

The psychrometric comparison in Figure 4 shows that Oslo has more annual outdoor conditions on the cold side of the comfort range, while Zurich has more hours in moderate temperature ranges. Outdoor air in Oslo therefore requires more often thermal conditioning before it can be supplied without reducing thermal comfort (Emmerich, 2006). This makes ventilation heat loss a central winter issue, especially in buildings with high fresh-air demand (Dimitroulopoulou & Bartzis, 2014; Laverge & Janssens, 2012). The diagram also points to the relevance of humidity, since cold outdoor air has low moisture content and can lead to low indoor relative humidity after heating (Alonso et al., 2015; Derby et al., 2017). Norwegian office measurements show that humidity, CO₂ and temperature are relevant IAQ indicators in low-energy office buildings (Justo Alonso et al., 2024). Nordic ventilation design should therefore consider temperature and humidity together, rather than treating airflow rate as the only performance indicator (Sundell et al., 2011; Wolkoff, 2018).

Figure 5 Dry bulb temperature chart of Oslo, Norway

Figure 6 Dry bulb temperature chart of Zurich, Switzerland

The yearly dry bulb comparison shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6 that Oslo has a longer and colder heating season than Zurich. The larger winter temperature difference between indoor air and outdoor air increases the potential for ventilation related heat losses (Laverge & Janssens, 2012). On the other hand, Oslo's lower summer temperatures reduce the risk of prolonged overheating and can lower active cooling demand compared with Zurich. The daily temperature differences are relevant because cooler nights can create potential for night ventilation during warm periods (Solgi et al., 2018). Nordic and cold-climate studies discuss night ventilation as a strategy for reducing overheating when outdoor conditions are favourable (Bakhtiari et al., 2020). In Zurich, night cooling can also be useful, but its effect may be reduced when night-time temperatures remain close to indoor comfort limits (Solgi et al., 2018). The dry-bulb comparison therefore shows a Nordic trade-off. Higher winter heating stress results in better summer potential for passive cooling with cooler outdoor air (Bakhtiari et al., 2020).

Figure 7 Incident radiation in winter and summer in Oslo, Norway and Zurich, Switzerland

The comparison of incident radiation helps to identify seasonal differences because solar gains affect both heating and cooling conditions (Prieto et al., 2017). In Oslo, limited winter radiation means that passive solar gains cannot compensate reliably for ventilation heat losses during the coldest months (see Figure 7). This reinforces the Nordic winter challenge. Conserving heat while maintaining sufficient IAQ (Alonso et al.,

2015). In summer, solar radiation can still contribute to overheating risk, especially in office buildings with high internal loads or large glazed areas (Grynning et al., 2014). However, Oslo's lower summer temperatures usually make cooling less important than in Zurich. Zurich therefore illustrates a climate where stronger summer heat exposure increases the importance of shading, cooling, and overheating control (Prieto et al., 2017)

Oslo and Zurich place different demands on ventilation design, even though both climates include heating and cooling considerations. In Oslo, the main challenge is to provide sufficient fresh air without excessive heat loss, low winter humidity, or cold-period discomfort (Justo Alonso et al., 2024). In Zurich, milder winters reduce the ventilation related heating penalty, while warmer summers increase cooling and overheating concerns. The Nordic climate therefore does not automatically favour one ventilation principle, but requires each strategy to be assessed against winter heat loss, dry indoor conditions, IAQ, and passive summer cooling potential (Rabani, Snderland, et al., 2025).

2.3 SUSTAINABILITY IN PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

Ventilation strategies influence sustainability beyond airflow provision. Their performance depends on operational energy, embodied emissions, indoor environmental quality, spatial consequences, investment costs, and long-term operation. The following sections review how recent peer-reviewed studies have evaluated environmental, social, and economic performance, providing a basis for comparing NV, HV, and MV in this thesis.

2.3.1 ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Recent studies commonly evaluate the environmental performance of ventilation systems through operational energy analysis and embodied emission consideration. Fong et al. (2017) applied LCA and LCC to compare three ventilation methods, considering energy demand, CO₂ emissions, and cost over production and operation phases. Kiamili et al. (Kiamili et al., 2020) assessed embodied carbon in HVAC systems using Building Information Modelling (BIM) and showed that technical installations can represent a substantial share of embodied impacts in office buildings. Ylmn et al. (2019) used site-specific data for a Swedish office building and showed that installations can have significant environmental impacts when contractor data are included. Decorte et al. (2024) confirmed that technical installations are increasingly important in whole-building LCA although their study was based on a single-family case rather than offices.

More recent Nordic ventilation research evaluates ventilation components and operational effects in greater detail. Bergsdal et al. (2024) developed life cycle inventory data for ventilation components, making it possible to assess embodied emissions from ducts, fittings, and air-handling components more consistently. Liu et al. (2024) optimized Norwegian ventilation ductwork by combining pressure-drop calculations, fan power, embodied emissions, and electricity-emission scenarios. Motuzien et al. (2024) used long-term monitoring of office buildings to show that inefficient MV operation can create energy performance gaps. Rabani et al. (2025) compared greenhouse gas emissions from natural, hybrid and mechanical ventilation. Mechanical ventilation had the highest embodied impact due to more ducts and technical components, while natural ventilation has the lowest.

2.3.2 SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY

The social performance of ventilation systems is usually evaluated through indoor environmental quality, thermal comfort, perceived control, occupant satisfaction, and health-related indicators. Gupta and Howard (2020) compared naturally and mechanically ventilated office environments using monitored indoor conditions and occupant surveys, showing that perceived satisfaction may differ from measured performance. Al Horr et al. (2016) reviewed office indoor environmental quality and linked thermal comfort, air quality, lighting, and acoustics to occupant productivity. Lassen et al. (2021) argued that subjective

occupant feedback is important in high-energy-performance office design because technical performance criteria alone may lead to suboptimal solutions.

Social performance is also strongly influenced by control strategy and user interaction. Lolli et al. (2024) tested predictive heating control in a Norwegian office and used questionnaires to assess perceived thermal comfort, control, well-being, luminous environment, noise, and perceived IAQ. Gobinath et al. (2025) reviewed smart HVAC control systems in commercial buildings and identified thermal comfort, IAQ, privacy, security, and employment as relevant social themes. Volf and Negendahl (2025) compared passive-controlled NV with MV with heat recovery in Danish residential renovation cases, including indoor environmental parameters alongside carbon and cost. Although that study is residential, it is relevant methodologically because it evaluates ventilation alternatives across both technical and user-related criteria.

2.3.3 ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

Economic performance is commonly evaluated through investment costs, operational energy costs, maintenance costs, replacement costs, and life cycle cost analysis. Fong et al. (2017) combined LCA with LCC and showed that ventilation alternatives can differ in both environmental impact and total cost. Kabbara et al. (2023) optimized centralized air-distribution systems in non-residential buildings and showed that ductwork layout and sizing influence system cost and performance. Justo Alonso et al. (2023) developed DCV strategies that reduced energy use while also reducing hours outside recommended IAQ limits. Niu et al. (2024) evaluated intermittent DCV and found that energy flexibility and cost benefits can be achieved without additional equipment investment.

Nordic and cold-climate studies also show that economic evaluation depends strongly on the selected boundary. Volf and Negendahl (2025) included capital cost, payback time, total cost, carbon footprint, and indoor environmental quality when comparing NV and MV in Danish residential renovation cases. Liu et al. (2025) used life cycle cost analysis for ventilation heat recovery in a Finnish hospital and showed that cost-optimal heat recovery depends on system sizing, energy tariffs, and long-term heating demand. Although hospital ventilation differs from office ventilation, the study is relevant because it demonstrates how high ventilation heat losses in Nordic climates can be evaluated economically. Motuzienė et al. (2024) further showed that monitored MV performance may deviate from design assumptions, which can affect operational energy cost.

2.3.4 HOLISTIC SUSTAINABILITY

Previous studies have evaluated the sustainability of ventilation systems with very different degrees of scope and integration. As shown in Table 2, environmental aspects are the most frequently addressed dimension, particularly operational energy use and embodied emissions. This reflects the traditional focus of ventilation research on reducing energy demand and climate impact. Social aspects are also considered in several studies, but they are mostly assessed through IAQ. Economic aspects are covered less frequently and usually appear through investment and operational costs or life cycle payback calculations. The table therefore shows that many studies contribute important knowledge on individual sustainability aspects, but only a smaller number combine environmental, social, and economic indicators in one assessment.

This comparison should not be understood as a complete representation of the entire research field, since only a limited number of studies were included in the review. However, based on the literature reviewed, a trend can be found. Previous research on ventilation systems is often sustainability-related, but not always holistic. Most studies focus on one or two dimensions, while fewer studies assess trade-offs between environmental performance, occupant-related outcomes, and economic consequences. This creates a research gap for assessments that compare ventilation strategies across several sustainability dimensions at the same time. For this thesis, the finding is important because the comparison of NV, HV, and MV should

not be based only on energy use or indoor climate. Instead, a broader framework is needed to understand how each strategy performs environmentally, socially, and economically within the same building context.

Study	Environmental			Social			Economic		
	Operational energy	Embodied emissions	Other environmental aspects	Indoor air quality	Perception / satisfaction / control	Health / well-being / productivity	Capital / investment cost	Operating / energy cost	Life cycle cost / payback
Fong et al. (2017)	✓	✓							✓
Kiamili et al. (2020)		✓							
Ylmén et al. (2019)	✓	✓	✓						
Decorte et al. (2024)	✓	✓	✓						
Bergsdal et al. (2024)		✓							
Liu, Tønnesen et al. (2024)	✓	✓							
Liu, Justo Alonso & Mathisen (2022)	✓								
Justo Alonso et al. (2022)	✓			✓					
Motuzienė et al. (2024)	✓								
Gupta & Howard (2020)				✓	✓				
Al Horr et al. (2016)				✓		✓			
Justo Alonso et al. (2024)				✓	✓				
Lassen et al. (2021)					✓				
Lolli et al. (2024)	✓			✓	✓	✓			
Gobinath et al. (2025)	✓			✓		✓			
Volf & Negendahl (2025)	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓
Kabbara et al. (2023)	✓						✓	✓	
Justo Alonso et al. (2023)	✓			✓					
Niu et al. (2024)	✓			✓				✓	
Liu, Ju et al. (2025)	✓						✓	✓	✓

Table 1 Literature review matrix

2.4 PREVIOUS THESIS ON VERTIKAL NYDALEN

The previous master thesis by Bekkeli (2021) is the most directly relevant case-specific study for this thesis. It compared the planned NV concept in Vertikal Nydalen with hypothetical HV and MV alternatives. The comparison focused on indoor climate, energy use, and GHG emissions and therefore provides an important technical and methodological foundation for this thesis. The study found that NV and HV can reduce delivered energy demand and GHG compared with a fully mechanical solution, but also that NV may create indoor climate challenges during critical winter and summer periods.

This thesis builds on Bekkeli's results but expands the assessment beyond the technical performance. While the previous thesis mainly evaluated indoor climate, energy demand, and GHG emissions, this thesis applies a broader sustainability framework including environmental, social, and economic dimensions. The assessment therefore also considers ecopoints, occupant comfort, design implications, daylight, investment costs, maintenance costs and energy costs. In this way, the study of Bekkeli (2021) functions both as a methodological reference and as a basis for evaluating how ventilation strategy affects sustainability more holistically.

2.4.1 METHODOLOGY APPROACH

Bekkeli (2021) used Vertikal Nydalen as a case study to compare three ventilation principles in the office part of the building. He evaluated the planned NV solution, a proposed HV and MV system. The NV scenario represented the original design concept of the building, while the hybrid and mechanical alternatives were developed as hypothetical comparison cases. This scenario-based structure is important for the present thesis because it allows the ventilation principle to be treated as the main comparative variable while the building context remains constant.

The previous thesis applied different methods for each performance area. Indoor climate was assessed through dynamic simulations in the software IDA ICE, where selected zones on the seventh floor were analysed regarding operative temperature, CO₂ concentration, air velocity, and predicted percentage dissatisfied (PPD). Energy performance was simulated using Simien, with results reported for both net energy demand and delivered energy demand. GHG emissions were calculated based on the simulated delivered energy use and material quantities from proposed ventilation system designs. The ventilation alternatives were therefore compared across operational and material-related impacts.

The scope of Bekkeli’s analysis was mainly limited to technical and environmental performance indicators. Social and economic aspects were discussed more indirectly, for example through indoor climate performance or reduced technical complexity but they were not developed into a broader multi-criteria sustainability framework. This creates the basis for the present thesis, which uses the previous technical results and scenario framework as a foundation for a more holistic assessment of ventilation strategies.

2.4.2 KEY FINDINGS

Bekkeli (2021) found that the choice of ventilation strategy involves a clear trade-off between indoor climate robustness, energy performance, and GHG emissions. NV showed strong environmental potential, especially because of reduced technical infrastructure and low delivered energy demand. However, the study also showed that a fully NV concept may create indoor climate challenges during critical periods. The main challenges were linked to draught, low indoor temperatures, and elevated CO₂ levels during winter, as well as overheating during summer.

HV performed as an intermediate solution. By combining NV with mechanical support, the hybrid strategy reduced several of the comfort risks found in the NV scenario while still maintaining some of its environmental advantages. This made HV a more balanced alternative, particularly for Nordic climate conditions where winter heat loss and thermal comfort are important concerns. MV provided the most stable and controllable indoor climate, but required more technical equipment, more space for installations, and higher material input.

Table 2 summarizes the main findings from Bekkeli (2021) and shows how the three ventilation strategies differ across indoor climate, energy performance, and climate impact. The results indicate that no single strategy performs best across all criteria. NV is environmentally promising but comfort-sensitive, MV is robust but technically intensive, and HV appears as a compromise between the two.

Scenario	Indoor Climate	Energy Performance	Climate Impact	Overall Interpretation
Natural ventilation	Weakest performance; risk of draught, low winter temperatures, high CO ₂ and overheating.	Weakest energy performance due to high heat losses.	Best climate performance due to low technical infrastructure and low operational energy.	Environmentally strongest, but most comfort-sensitive.
Hybrid ventilation	Intermediate performance; mechanical support reduced comfort risks.	Best energy performance due to lower heat losses and limited fan energy.	Intermediate climate impact.	Most balanced solution between comfort and environmental performance.
Mechanical ventilation	Best and most stable indoor climate due to controlled supply and extract airflow.	Intermediate energy performance; fan energy higher, but heat recovery reduced losses.	Highest climate impact due to more equipment, ductwork and operational energy.	Technically robust, but environmentally least favourable.

Table 2 Key finding summary previous master thesis

2.4.3 EXTENSION OF PREVIOUS RESEARCH

This study builds on the research of Bekkeli (2021) by extending the assessment of ventilation strategies in Vertikal Nydalen from a primarily technical and environmental comparison to a broader sustainability evaluation. Bekkeli's study mainly addressed environmental sustainability through energy demand and GHG emissions, while social sustainability was considered more indirectly through indoor climate indicators such as operative temperature, CO₂ concentration, air velocity, and PPD. Economic sustainability was not treated as an independent assessment category. As a result, the previous thesis provides a valuable technical foundation, but does not fully address the wider implications of ventilation strategy for sustainable office design.

Figure 8 Extension of previous research

This thesis contributes by evaluating NV, HV, and MV according to all three dimensions of sustainability (see Figure 8). The environmental assessment includes energy demand, GHG emissions, and ecopoints. The social assessment considers occupant comfort, design aspects, and daylight conditions, while the economic assessment includes investment costs, maintenance costs, and energy costs. By applying this broader framework, the thesis enables a more structured comparison of the trade-offs between the three ventilation strategies. This is particularly relevant in a Nordic office context, where reduced technical complexity and lower environmental impact must be balanced against indoor climate reliability, architectural consequences, and cost implications. The contribution of this thesis is therefore not to replace the findings of Bekkeli (2021), but to reinterpret and expand them within a more comprehensive sustainability framework.

3 METHODOLOGY

A structured methodology was developed to compare the three ventilation scenarios within the selected office area of Vertikal Nydalen. It begins by defining the case study boundary and scenario setup, followed by the methods for assessing environmental, social and economic performance.

3.1 CASE STUDY BUILDING

This chapter introduces GT2A as the case study basis for the comparative assessment conducted in this thesis. The building was selected because it provides a real-world example of NV in a Nordic office context. Its innovative ventilation concept, urban cold-climate location and existing technical investigations make it a suitable foundation for comparing alternative ventilation strategies.

3.1.1 LOCATION

Vertikal Nydalen is located at GT2A site in the Nydalen district of Oslo, Norway. Nydalen lies in the upper valley of the Akerselva river (see Figure 9) and has historically been shaped by industrial activity. Textile production played an important role in the area's development from the mid-nineteenth century onward, particularly through Nydalens Compagnie (Nydalen, 2024). Metal industry also became central to the district's identity through Christiania Spigerverk. Since the 1990s, Nydalen has undergone substantial urban transformation. Former industrial areas have gradually been redeveloped into a district characterized by offices, housing, education, services, and commercial activity (Nydalen – Oslo Byleksikon, n.d.). Avantor has been a central actor in this redevelopment and states that it has developed more than 600,000 m² of new buildings and major refurbishment projects in the area (Avantor, n.d.). Vertikal Nydalen forms part of this wider transformation. The project replaced a former parking-lot site at Gullhaug Torg with a mixed-use building. The building contains restaurants and shared functions at the lower levels, offices on the middle floors, and apartments above (Snøhetta, 2024).

Figure 9 Site plan Vertika Nydalen, Gullhaug Torg 2A (Snøhetta, n.d.-b)

3.1.2 BUILDING FUNCTION

GT2A was developed as a mixed-use building that combines office spaces, commercial functions, and residential units within two interconnected building volumes totaling approximately 10,000 m² (Figure 10). This functional diversity reflects the broader urban redevelopment strategy of Nydalen, where former industrial areas have been transformed into integrated districts that combine working, living, and service functions. Within the context of this thesis, the office component is of primary relevance, as it constitutes the basis for evaluating and comparing different ventilation strategies in a Nordic office environment (Bekkeli, 2021).

Figure 10 Section of Vertikal Nydalen with mixed-use and ventilation overview (Snøhetta, n.d.-a)

3.1.3 ARCHITECTURAL CONCEPT

The architectural concept of Vertikal Nydalen was developed as an integrated response to both environmental performance goals and functional office design. Rather than treating technical systems as separate from architectural form, the project aimed to align building geometry, facade design, and internal spatial organization with climate-responsive strategies. A central design objective was to use the building's shape and orientation to create favourable pressure conditions for natural airflow, thereby supporting ventilation performance through architectural means. According to prior project documentation, airflow simulations were used to optimize the form to maximize cross-ventilation potential under varying weather conditions.

This integration of architecture and building physics also influenced interior design quality. By reducing reliance on extensive duct infrastructure, the concept sought to preserve ceiling height, spatial openness, and architectural clarity while minimizing technical complexity. The project therefore represents an example of how passive or low-mechanical design principles can shape not only building performance, but also the experiential and spatial qualities of office environments. For this thesis, the architectural concept is particularly relevant because it directly affects both the feasibility of the NV strategy and the design implications of hypothetical alternative systems.

3.1.4 SUSTAINABILITY AMBITIONS

Vertikal Nydalen was conceived as part of the broader Nydalen+ urban development strategy and was intended to function as a demonstrator project for sustainable building innovation in Oslo. In collaboration with organizations such as FutureBuilt and the Naturligvis research initiative, the project aimed to explore how architectural and technical integration could contribute to lower energy demand, reduced technical infrastructure, and improved long-term building performance.

A major environmental ambition was the reduction of operational energy use through climate-adapted building design and reduced dependence on conventional MV systems. Simplified technical systems were expected to lower embodied impacts, reduce maintenance requirements, and potentially decrease investment costs. These ambitions align closely with the environmental and economic dimensions of this thesis.

Beyond technical efficiency, the project also pursued social sustainability goals by emphasizing occupant experience, architectural quality, and workplace attractiveness. The intention was not only to create a lower-impact building, but also to demonstrate that sustainable office design could improve user experience through greater spatial quality and integrated environmental strategies. This broader sustainability orientation strengthens the relevance of Vertikal Nydalen as a case study for a holistic sustainability assessment (Snøhetta, 2024).

3.1.5 VENTILATION CONCEPT

The ventilation concept of Vertikal Nydalen is central to both the building's identity and the research focus of this thesis. Unlike conventional Nordic office buildings that primarily depend on balanced MV, Vertikal Nydalen's office areas were designed around NV principles, where airflow is supported through facade-integrated openings, pressure differences, and building form optimization. This strategy was intended to reduce the need for extensive mechanical duct systems while maintaining acceptable indoor environmental quality.

To support this concept, the building geometry was optimized through aerodynamic analyses to enhance natural pressure differentials and improve cross-ventilation effectiveness. Facade openings and ventilation elements are used to regulate air supply and extract airflow in response to external climatic conditions. The design also incorporates complementary heating solutions to address seasonal challenges associated with Oslo's cold winters, where NV alone may create thermal comfort limitations. This reflects a climate-adapted strategy that attempts to balance passive ventilation benefits with Nordic operational realities.

The significance of this ventilation concept lies in its departure from standard practice. By embedding ventilation into the architecture itself, the project reduces technical infrastructure requirements and may lower embodied emissions and maintenance complexity. However, this approach also introduces uncertainties regarding year-round comfort performance, control reliability, and adaptability under extreme weather conditions. These tensions are directly relevant to the thesis, as the NV system serves as the baseline against which hybrid and mechanical alternatives are assessed across environmental, social, and economic sustainability categories.

Because ventilation strategy forms the core comparative variable of this research, understanding the as-built NV concept is essential for defining realistic alternative scenarios and interpreting broader sustainability trade-offs. Vertikal Nydalen therefore provides not only a practical case, but also a testbed for examining whether NV principles can meaningfully compete with more conventional ventilation systems in future Nordic office design (Bekkei, 2021).

3.1.6 SCOPE AND BOUNDARIES

This thesis focuses exclusively on the office component of GT2A as the defined physical boundary of the case study. Although the building itself is a mixed-use development comprising office spaces, commercial

functions, and residential units, only the office areas are included in this research. Residential and commercial functions are excluded in order to maintain a clear and consistent analytical framework centered on a single building use type with comparable occupancy patterns, spatial demands, and operational characteristics (Bekkeli, 2021).

Within the office component, the scope is further limited to selected areas on the seventh floor of the northern building block (see Figure 11). This floor was identified in the previous thesis as a representative section due to its combination of open-plan office spaces, meeting rooms, and supporting functions with varying spatial and occupancy conditions (Bekkeli, 2021). By focusing on a single floor rather than the entire office building, the study establishes a manageable and clearly defined case study area while still reflecting the broader architectural and functional characteristics of Vertikal Nydalen's office concept.

The boundaries of this thesis are therefore defined by three principal limitations. The exclusion of all non-office functions, the restriction to the northern building block and the concentration on the seventh floor as the representative study area. These physical boundaries provide a coherent framework for the thesis and ensure that subsequent analyses are grounded in a realistic, clearly delimited, and methodologically consistent section of the overall building.

Figure 11 Definition of the case study boundary: selected office area on the 7th floor of Vertikal Nydalen

3.2 VENTILATION SCENARIOS FOR COMPARISON

This thesis compares three ventilation scenarios based on the representative office spaces on the seventh floor of Vertikal Nydalen's northern building block. The comparative framework follows the scenario structure established by Bekkeli (2021), thereby ensuring methodological continuity with the previous master thesis while expanding the assessment toward a broader sustainability perspective. By using the same case floor, spatial conditions, and general building framework across all scenarios, ventilation strategy becomes the primary variable of comparison.

The three scenarios consist of the existing NV concept as built, a hypothetical HV model, and a hypothetical demand-controlled MV model (see Figure 12). The ventilation scenarios are not intended as complete building redesigns, but rather as comparative system alternatives applied within the same physical building boundary. This ensures that differences in sustainability performance can be more clearly attributed to ventilation strategy rather than unrelated architectural or functional variables.

Figure 12 Floor plans with ventilation scenarios based on Bekkeli (2021)

3.2.1 NATURAL VENTILATION (AS BUILT)

The NV scenario represents the real as-built ventilation concept of Vertikal Nydalen and serves as the baseline case for this thesis. It is based on the building's original climate-responsive design strategy, where façade openings, automated ventilation hatches and pressure optimised building geometry support airflow mainly through natural driving forces such as wind pressure and thermal buoyancy. The open office areas are fully naturally ventilated through façade openings. In contrast, the meeting rooms are supported by a small AHU, which supplies additional air due to the higher occupancy density and associated airflow demand in these spaces. As the supply air is not preheated by the AHU, it is distributed through so-called climate canoes consisting of perforated wooden panels. These elements spread the incoming air more evenly and reduce the risk of draught in the occupied zone. The toilets are served by a central extract air system, which removes used air from the sanitary areas.

3.2.2 HYBRID VENTILATION (HYPOTHETICAL)

The HV scenario is based on the comparative model developed by Bekkeli (2021) represents an intermediate strategy between the NV and MV approaches. It combines the existing principles of NV with mechanical supply air support and heat recovery during winter operation. This addresses some of the seasonal limitations of pure NV in Oslo's cold climate. The HV concept uses the same number of façade openings as the NV scenario, but does not include the climate canoes and the small AHU. It is assumed that the meeting rooms receive fresh air through the MV system, as these rooms have higher occupancy densities and therefore require more stable airflow. The open office areas, however, are mainly assumed to be partly naturally ventilated, especially during periods with favourable outdoor temperatures and during peak occupancy when additional airflow is required. The duct system supplies fresh air to all rooms, but is dimensioned smaller than in the MV scenario because the façade openings can cover part of the peak airflow demand.

3.2.3 MECHANICAL VENTILATION (HYPOTHETICAL)

The MV scenario is likewise based on the framework established by Bekkeli (2021) and serves as the conventional benchmark for comparison. This model applies a DCV system with fully mechanical air supply and extraction together with heat recovery, representing a more traditional Nordic office ventilation solution. Compared to the natural and hybrid alternatives, the MV scenario prioritizes controlled and predictable indoor climate regulation through technical infrastructure rather than architectural or passive

climatic strategies. This typically allows more precise control of airflow and thermal conditions, but also increases technical complexity, space requirements and system dependency. Since the MV scenario is not supported by a passive ventilation system, it must provide the full required airflow mechanically. As a result, both the ductwork and the AHU are dimensioned larger than in the HV scenario.

3.3 EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

The framework was developed to compare the NV, HV and MV scenarios within the same case study boundary (see Figure 14). It builds on the scenario logic established in the previous technical comparison of Vertikal Nydalen but extended the assessment from mainly technical and environmental performance towards a broader sustainability evaluation. The framework was structured as a top-down process. First, each ventilation scenario was assessed according to three sustainability dimensions. Each dimension was represented by three indicators (see Figure 13).

Figure 13 Criteria overview of evaluation framework

For the evaluation framework a four-step approach was chosen:

1. In the first step, each indicator was analysed separately. Each indicator was calculated or assessed using the method most suitable for the available data and the character of the indicator. Quantitative indicators, such as energy demand, emissions, ecopoints and costs, were evaluated through numerical calculations. More design-related indicators were assessed through defined qualitative or performance-based criteria.
2. The second step translated the individual findings into a common point system. This was necessary because the indicators had different units and could not be compared directly. Energy demand was expressed in kilowatt-hours, emissions in CO₂ equivalents, costs in monetary values, and social or design-related aspects through spatial and performance-based criteria. The point system thus standardised the results and made it possible to compare the relative performance of the three scenarios for each indicator. The scoring was comparative and case-specific. It did not represent an absolute certification of sustainability, but a structured ranking within the defined boundary of this thesis.
3. The third step combined the nine indicator scores in one summary chart. This chart provided an overview of how each ventilation scenario performed across the complete set of environmental, social and economic criteria. It showed strengths and weaknesses at indicator level and made trade-offs visible. For example, a scenario could perform well in environmental terms but less strongly in comfort, daylight or cost-related aspects.
4. In the final step, the nine indicator scores were further condensed into three overall sustainability profiles: environmental, social and economic performance. This final overview provided a simplified comparison of the NV, HV and MV scenarios at the level of the three sustainability dimensions. The

framework therefore moved from detailed indicator analysis to an integrated sustainability overview. This structure supported a balanced interpretation of the results and prevented the final comparison from being based on only one criterion.

A scale from 1 to 5 was chosen to illustrate the relative differences between the ventilation scenarios. The scale was deliberately not made more detailed, because the framework included several parameters and the research depth for each individual indicator was therefore limited. A more detailed scale could have suggested a level of precision that the study could not fully support. The selected five-point scale therefore made the comparative results transparent, while avoiding an exaggerated impression of accuracy. The point system normalised the results and made it possible to compare the relative performance of the three scenarios within each indicator. The scoring was comparative and case-specific. It did not represent an absolute certification of sustainability, but a structured ranking within the defined boundary of this thesis.

Quantitative indicators were scored based on the relative differences between the three scenarios. Qualitative indicators were scored using predefined criteria, including technical visibility, spatial impact, daylight effect and available comfort evidence. The score therefore shows how the scenarios perform in comparison with each other within this case study. It should not be understood as an absolute assessment of the general quality of each ventilation system.

Figure 14 Concept of evaluation framework

3.3.1 QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

The quantitative evaluation was used to translate the indicators with numerical results into a common point system. This was necessary because the indicators were measured in different units and could not be compared directly. For example, primary energy was expressed as kWh, emissions as kg CO₂-equivalents, ecopoints as a weighted environmental score, and costs as NOK/m² or NOK/m²a. To make these results comparable within the overall sustainability framework, the numerical values were converted into a common score from 1 to 5.

The formula-based evaluation was applied to all indicators where numerical results were available. These included primary energy demand, greenhouse gas emissions, ecopoints, investment costs, maintenance

costs and energy costs. For these indicators, a lower value represents better performance. Therefore, the following formula was used:

$$S_n = 1 + 3 \cdot \frac{x_{\max} - x_n}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}$$

For indicators where a higher value represents better performance, such as the results of the occupant satisfaction level this formula was reversed:

$$S_n = 1 + 3 \cdot \frac{x_n - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}$$

S_n represents the score of scenario n (1-5)

x_n is the numerical result of scenario n (kWh, NOK/m², etc.)

x_{\min} is the lowest value among the three scenarios, and (kWh, NOK/m², etc.)

x_{\max} is the highest value among the three scenarios (kWh, NOK/m², etc.)

The formula gives the weakest scenario 1 point and the best-performing scenario within the case-study comparison 4 points. A score of 5 was not assigned automatically. It was reserved for cases where a result also meets or exceeds an external benchmark, target value or clearly defined excellent performance level. This was done in second step qualitatively. This approach was chosen to avoid presenting the best performing scenario in the comparison as an absolute optimum. The scoring therefore remains comparative and context specific. It demonstrates how natural, hybrid and mechanical ventilation perform relative to one another within the defined scope of this thesis, whilst acknowledging that a higher level of performance may exist beyond the three scenarios assessed.

3.3.2 QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

Qualitative assessment was used for indicators that could not be directly translated into a numerical calculation. This applied to design aspects as well as parts of the daylight assessment where performance was influenced more by spatial, visual and architectural qualities than by a single measurable value. These indicators were therefore converted to a 1–5-point scale using predefined evaluation criteria rather than a quantitative formula.

For the design evaluation, the scenarios were assessed in terms of their impact on the visibility of technical elements, the spatial effect, ceiling height and architectural integration. This took into account the extent to which each ventilation strategy required visible ducts, technical equipment and suspended ceiling surfaces, and the extent to which this altered the original spatial character of the office area. For the daylight assessment, the scenarios were evaluated according to how the design changes necessitated by the ventilation affected daylight conditions. The main criteria were ceiling height, the openness of the space, visual obstructions caused by technical installations, and the effects of opaque or transparent ventilation openings. The daylight analysis was therefore interpreted as a relative comparison of the extent to which each ventilation strategy influenced daylight availability and spatial perception.

The final assessment on a scale of 1 to 5 was based on a structured evaluation using these criteria. A high score indicated limited spatial or daylight-related impacts, whilst a low score reflected more significant visual, spatial or daylight-related consequences.

3.4 ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT METHODS

Environmental performance was assessed through the indicators energy demand, GHG emissions and ecopoints. These indicators were selected to represent different levels of environmental impact, from operational resource use to climate impact and broader ecological effects. All three parameters were calculated using a LCA approach. The assessment included both embodied impacts from the materials and components used in each ventilation scenario and operational impacts during the use phase.

3.4.1 ENERGY DEMAND

In order to include operational impacts in the LCA, the annual delivered energy demand was defined for each ventilation scenario. The energy values were used to represent module B6 and therefore form the basis for the operational part of the environmental assessment. In the previous study, Bekkeli (2021) simulated the NV, HV and MV scenarios in SIMIEN before Vertikal Nydalen was constructed. The same study reported both net and delivered energy demand and used the simulated values as input for the GHG assessment of the ventilation alternatives.

For this thesis, the data basis for the NV scenario was updated. Since the building has now been in operation for several years, measured energy data from the office area was available. This data was provided by Skanska and was used instead of the pre-construction simulation for the as-built NV case. The measured data was assumed to be representative for the office floors in the building. It was therefore applied to the investigated area of 518 m² on the seventh floor. The HV and MV scenarios remained hypothetical alternatives. For these two scenarios, the simulated delivered energy demand from Bekkeli (2021) was retained, as no measured operational data exists for these systems.

The difference between the simulated and measured NV demand is substantial. In the original simulation, the total delivered energy demand for NV was 69.7 kWh/m²a. The measured data shows a total delivered energy demand of 40.3 kWh/m²a. The largest difference occurs in space heating, which decreases from 21.8 kWh/m²a in the simulation to 4.5 kWh/m²a in the measured data. This indicates that the actual heat losses caused by façade openings were considerably lower than expected in the pre-construction model. According to WindowMaster, which was responsible for the NV system in Vertikal Nydalen, heat losses from window-based ventilation in offices are often lower than predicted because internal gains from occupants, lighting and technical equipment partly compensate for the heat loss during operation.

Table 3 presents the delivered energy demand of the three ventilation scenarios. In line with Bekkeli (2021), only energy categories directly affected by the ventilation principle were included in the operational LCA comparison. These categories were space heating, ventilation heating, space cooling, ventilation cooling, fans and pumps. Domestic hot water, lighting and plug loads were excluded from the comparative LCA input because they are not directly determined by the ventilation strategy and are therefore not suitable for distinguishing between the scenarios. Based on this boundary, the measured NV scenario has a ventilation-related delivered energy demand of 5.5 kWh/m²a, compared with 10.1 kWh/m²a for HV and 13.0 kWh/m²a for MV. The updated operational data therefore strengthens the relevance of the NV case as the real baseline scenario, while the hybrid and mechanical cases remain simulation-based comparison alternatives.

This mixed data basis was directly considered when interpreting the results. The value for NV is based on measured operation in the realised building. In contrast, the values for the HV and MV scenarios are based on hypothetical performance from previous simulations. The differences between the scenarios therefore reflect both the ventilation strategy and the type of evidence used. For this reason, the energy results were not interpreted as three equally verified operational measurements. Instead, they were assessed together with the robustness of the underlying data.

Energy Demand	Natural Ventilation [kWh/m ² a]	Natural Ventilation [kWh/m ² a]	Hybrid Ventilation [kWh/m ² a]	Mechanical Ventilation [kWh/m ² a]
1a Space Heating	4.5	21.8	4.5	0.2
1b Ventilation Heating	0	0	0.3	1.1
2 Domestic Hot Water	3.1	1.8	1.8	1.8
3a Space Cooling	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.6
3b Ventilation Cooling	0	0	0.1	1.6
4a-b Fans and Pumps	0.7	2.6	5	9.5
5 Lighting	11.1	9.4	9.4	9.4
6 Plug Loads	20.6	33.9	33.9	33.9
Total	40.3	69.7	55.2	58.1
Total (1a-b, 3a-b, 4a-b)	5.5	24.6	10.1	13.0
Data Source	Measured - Skanska	Simulated - Bekkeli (2021)	Simulated - Bekkeli (2021)	Simulated - Bekkeli (2021)

Table 3 Operational energy demand of different ventilation scenarios

3.4.2 LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

The GHG emissions were calculated through LCA in One Click LCA. The software was used because it combines several LCA databases and Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) in one calculation environment. The calculation followed the European Standard EN 15804 as the underlying framework for product-related environmental data. However, the assessment was not designed as a complete cradle-to-grave LCA. To remain comparable with Bekkeli (2021), the system boundary was limited to the product stage A1–A3, replacement during the use stage B4, and operational energy use B6. Construction, transport to site, installation, maintenance, end-of-life processes and benefits beyond the system boundary were excluded (see Figure 15). The assessment therefore focused on the parameters most directly affected by the ventilation strategy. This was material quantities, expected component lifetimes, replacements during the reference period and delivered energy demand.

The material inventory was developed differently for the three scenarios. For the NV scenario, Bekkeli (2021) only included the actuators used for the automated façade openings. This was sufficient for the pre-construction comparison, but it did not fully describe the as-built system in Vertikal Nydalen. In this thesis, the material scope of the NV case was expanded. In addition to the window actuators, the climate canoes, the extract-air system serving bathrooms and other sanitary rooms, and the supporting fans connected to the NV concept were included. This gives a more detailed representation of the embodied impact of the realised NV system.

For the HV and MV scenarios, the material quantities were retained from Bekkeli (2021), since these alternatives remain hypothetical comparison cases and were not developed further as detailed design solutions in this thesis. The quantities therefore provide a consistent basis for comparing the additional material demand of more technically intensive ventilation strategies. The environmental datasets used in the updated calculation were not identical to those applied in the previous study. Where product-specific EPDs were unavailable or where a direct product match could not be verified, average datasets from One Click LCA were selected. This approach was chosen to avoid both underestimation and overestimation from overly specific product assumptions. As a result, the emission values are not directly identical to Bekkeli (2021), even where the material quantities are the same. EPDs with average emissions values were chosen instead. The comparison with the previous thesis must therefore be interpreted as a methodological continuation with updated data, not as a one-to-one recalculation of the earlier results. The material quantities of each ventilation scenario can be found in Appendix A-C.

Figure 15 Overview of evaluated life cycle stages

3.4.3 GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS AND PRIMARY ENERGY

GHG emissions and primary energy were used to describe two different environmental consequences of the ventilation scenarios. GHG emissions were assessed through global warming potential (GWP) and expressed as kg CO₂-equivalents. This indicator was used to evaluate the climate impact of material use, component replacements and operational energy demand associated with each ventilation strategy. It therefore allowed the comparison to include both embodied and operational contributions within one result, which was important because the scenarios differ strongly in technical complexity.

Primary energy was included as a complementary indicator, since it describes the total energy resources required across the life cycle rather than only the energy delivered to the building during operation. This was relevant because ventilation systems differ not only in operational demand, but also in the amount of technical equipment and material input required. The primary energy results were extracted from the same One Click LCA model as the emission results. For this assessment, One Click LCA applied Norwegian primary energy factors, so the results reflected the national energy context of the case study. Both indicators were normalised to the defined floor area, enabling a direct and consistent comparison between the NV, HV and MV scenarios.

3.4.4 ECOPOINT CLASSIFICATION

For the ecopoint calculation, several single-score environmental assessment systems were first reviewed. The purpose was to identify a method that could translate the LCA results into one comparable environmental score without reducing the assessment to climate change alone. Four alternatives were considered. The European Environmental Footprint Method provides a weighted score based on characterised Life Cycle Impact Assessment results and covers 16 environmental impact categories (European Commission, 2021). The related product and organisation environmental footprint application follows the same European logic, but is primarily intended for product or organisation level reporting. The Swiss Umweltbelastungspunkte method is based on ecological scarcity and applies eco-factors to inventory flows, which makes it detailed but less suitable when only characterised indicator results are available. The ecopoints of Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) UK also provides a single weighted score, but its Environmental Profiles method is based on 13 impact indicators (BRE Global Limited, 2014). The European Environmental Footprint method was therefore selected because

it covered the largest number of environmental parameters that could be linked to the EN 15804-based LCA output from One Click LCA.

The ecopoint calculation used the available impact categories shown marked in Table 4 as the basis for comparison. These included acidification, climate change, eutrophication of freshwater, marine and terrestrial environments, photochemical ozone formation, resource depletion of fossil resources and resource depletion of minerals and metals. Consequently, the results do not represent a complete European Environmental Footprint score and should not be compared with projects that apply the full method. The calculation is nevertheless suitable for the purpose of this thesis because the same reduced boundary was applied consistently to all ventilation scenarios.

The method uses two steps to convert different environmental indicators into one score. First, each characterised result is divided by a normalisation factor. This factor represents the reference environmental impact per person for the respective category and makes indicators with different units comparable. Second, the normalised result is multiplied by a weighting factor. This factor expresses the relative importance assigned to the impact category within the European Environmental Footprint method. The original weighting factors were kept unchanged, although only a reduced set of categories was used. They were not rescaled to 100%, because the relationship between the included categories would remain the same. For the comparative assessment, this is sufficient. The ecopoint results indicate the relative environmental performance of the NV, HV and MV scenarios within the defined system boundary.

Impact categories	Unit	NF	WF [%]
Acidification	mol H+ eq./person	56	6.20%
Climate change	kg CO2 eq./person	7553	21.06%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe/person	56717	1.92%
EF-particulate matter	disease incidences/person	0.0006	8.96%
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq./person	1.6	2.80%
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq./person	19.5	2.96%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq./person	177	3.71%
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh/person	0.000017	2.13%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh/person	0.00013	1.84%
Ionising radiation	kBq U-235 eq./person	4220	5.01%
Land use*	pt/person	819498	7.94%
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq./person	0.052	6.31%
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq./person	41	4.78%
Resource depletion, fossils	MJ/person	65004	8.32%
Resource depletion, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq./person	0.064	7.55%
Water use*	m3 water eq of deprived water/person	11469	8.51%

Table 4 Ecopoint categories and weighting factors

3.5 SOCIAL ASSESSMENT METHODS

The social assessment evaluated how the ventilation strategies affected occupants and spatial experience. Three aspects were analysed: perceived comfort, architectural design implications and daylight conditions. Together, these methods linked user feedback with design-based consequences of NV, HV and MV in the selected office area.

3.5.1 OCCUPANT COMFORT ANALYSIS

Occupant comfort was assessed using existing feedback data from office buildings with NV, HV and MV systems. The main data source was survey material collected by Skanska across several Norwegian buildings.

These surveys provided a basis for comparing how users perceive indoor environmental quality under different ventilation principles. For Vertikal Nydalen, the assessment also included feedback continuously collected through QR codes in the building. This made it possible to include post-occupancy experience from the as-built NV scenario, rather than relying only on simulated performance or pre-construction assumptions.

The comfort analysis focused on perceived satisfaction with the indoor environment, especially thermal comfort, air quality and user experience. This was relevant because previous technical evaluations of Vertikal Nydalen showed that NV may reduce energy demand and emissions, but can also create comfort risks during critical winter and summer periods (Bekkeli, 2021). The availability of comparable literature was limited for naturally ventilated Nordic office buildings, since Vertikal Nydalen represents one of the few realised examples of this type in the region. For HV and MV, additional literature and survey-based studies from other projects were therefore considered to support the interpretation of the results. The final assessment was comparative and focused on how each ventilation scenario performed within the wider social sustainability framework.

Because the available comfort datasets were not identical, the survey results were not treated as a strict statistical comparison. The extracted indicators included perceived temperature, air quality, draught, noise, perceived control and overall satisfaction where these categories were available. Feedback from Vertikal Nydalen was used as the most case-specific evidence for the NV scenario, while data from other Norwegian buildings and literature supported the interpretation of the HV and MV scenarios. The 1–5 score therefore reflected a comparative interpretation of comfort tendencies, supported by the robustness of each data source, rather than a direct numerical average across all surveys.

3.5.2 DESIGN ANALYSIS

The design analysis evaluated how the three ventilation scenarios affected the visual and spatial quality of the office areas. The BIM model provided by Snøhetta was used as the architectural reference. The ventilation models from Bekkeli (2021) were integrated into this model to compare the alternatives within the same spatial context. The NV scenario was assessed as the as-built reference, where air supply is integrated into the façade and no conventional supply duct network is visible in the office space.

For the HV and MV scenarios, two spatial variants were analysed. The first variant kept the ceiling open and exposed the ductwork and technical components. The second variant introduced a lowered ceiling to cover the installations. A ceiling reduction of 30 cm was assumed for the HV scenario and 60 cm for the MV scenario. The larger reduction in the MV scenario reflected the higher airflow demand and the larger duct dimensions required for a fully MV supply and extract system.

For the natural and HV scenarios, the façade ventilation openings were also tested as opaque and transparent elements. The transparent variant was included as an experimental option to explore the possible visual and daylight effect of admitting additional light through the openings. This does not describe the actual solution in Vertikal Nydalen, where the openings include sound-insulating layers because of outdoor noise. The models were rendered in Twinmotion to create comparable visual material for assessing technical visibility, ceiling height, openness and façade expression. Consistent camera positions, material settings and lighting conditions were applied so scenario differences remained comparable and not dependent on rendering style alone.

3.5.3 DAYLIGHT ANALYSIS

The daylight analysis examined whether the ventilation scenarios influenced daylight availability in the representative office areas. The analysis was carried out in Rhino using Grasshopper and Ladybug. The architectural model was simplified to the relevant study area and used as a common geometric basis for all scenarios. This ensured that differences in the results were linked to ventilation-related design parameters rather than changes in room layout or façade geometry.

Two effects were investigated. The first was the influence of lowered ceilings in the HV and MV scenarios. A reduced ceiling height can affect the spatial perception of the room and may also influence daylight distribution through changes in internal reflecting surfaces. The HV scenario was therefore analysed with a 30 cm ceiling reduction, while the MV scenario was analysed with a 60 cm reduction. Both were compared with the NV reference, where no lowered ceiling was required for a conventional duct network.

The second effect was the possible daylight contribution from transparent ventilation openings. For the natural and HV scenarios, opaque and transparent variants were simulated. The transparent variant was included as an experimental design option and not as a representation of the as-built solution at Vertikal Nydalen. The daylight results were used to compare the relative impact of the ventilation concepts and were included as one part of the social assessment, rather than as a full daylight certification or compliance study.

The simulation setup was kept constant for all scenarios. The same analysis grid, sensor height, façade geometry, glazing properties and internal surface assumptions were used in each model variant. Furniture and detailed interior objects were excluded unless they directly affected the daylight path, in order to keep the comparison focused on ventilation-related design changes. The daylight results were therefore interpreted as relative differences between scenarios rather than as exact predictions of final workplace illuminance. The same principle was applied when translating the simulation results into the evaluation framework, where the score reflected the comparative daylight impact of ceiling height and transparent or opaque ventilation openings. The detailed settings of the simulation can be found in Appendix D.

3.6 ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT METHODS

Economic performance was assessed through investment costs, maintenance costs and energy costs. These indicators were selected because they represent the main cost consequences affected by the ventilation strategy. The assessment was comparative and case-specific. It did not constitute a full life cycle cost analysis, but provided a structured basis for evaluating economic trade-offs between the three scenarios.

3.6.1 INVESTMENT COST ESTIMATION

Investment costs were estimated to compare the initial cost consequences of the three ventilation strategies within the same office-floor boundary. The calculation used cost values in Norwegian kroner per square metre, so that the results could be compared independently of system size and later scaled to the investigated floor area. The aim was not to produce a tender-level cost estimate, but to establish a robust comparative estimate based on the available data.

Several data sources were reviewed in order to reduce dependence on a single reference value. For the NV scenario, the most case-specific basis was the investment cost of the realised façade-integrated NV system in Vertikal Nydalen. This information was provided by WindowMaster, which supplied the NV system for the project. This source was therefore treated as the primary reference for the as-built scenario. Additional benchmark values from reports and previous studies were used to check whether the case-specific value was within a reasonable cost range.

For the HV and MV scenarios, no project-specific investment costs were available, because both alternatives are hypothetical comparison cases. Their estimates therefore had to be derived from external benchmarks, comparable projects, supplier input, published reports and Norsk Prisbok. The HV scenario was interpreted as a reduced mechanical system combined with automated NV components, while the MV scenario was interpreted as a DCV system. Each source was reviewed in relation to system scope, included components and relevance to Norwegian office buildings. Where sources differed, the values were not treated as exact prices, but as a range of plausible investment levels. The investment boundary included ventilation components, control elements and system-related installation costs where these were identifiable in the available sources. Costs for unrelated architectural works, structural adaptations, general contractor

overhead, design fees and value-added tax were excluded unless they were explicitly part of a source value and could not be separated.

3.6.2 MAINTENANCE COST CALCULATION

Maintenance costs were calculated to represent the recurring operational effort required to keep each ventilation strategy functional during the use phase. The assessment used annual cost values in Norwegian kroner per square metre and year. As with the investment estimate, several sources were compared to improve the reliability of the assumptions and to avoid basing the result on a single benchmark. The NV estimate was supported by the actual Vertikal Nydalen system, where WindowMaster supplied the façade-integrated NV solution and is also responsible for maintenance during operation. This made the NV case more directly grounded in the realised project than the two hypothetical alternatives. For the HV and MV scenarios, no actual maintenance records exist. The assumptions were therefore based on benchmark values from reports, comparable projects, Norsk Prisbok and supplier-related information.

Maintenance was defined as routine inspection, servicing, adjustment, testing and documentation required during normal operation. For NV, this included window actuators, opening mechanisms, façade-integrated ventilation openings, sensors, control software, the weather, rain and wind station, the building management system interface, remote monitoring, function testing and reporting. Maintenance of AHUs, filters, fans and ductwork was not included unless such components were part of separate systems within the scenario boundary. For HV, the scope included relevant mechanical DCV maintenance for a reduced mechanical system, in addition to actuators, opening mechanisms, weather and indoor sensors, control software, building management system integration, remote monitoring, function testing and reporting. For MV, the scope included annual contractor inspection, filter replacement, fan and motor checks, AHU inspection, heat-recovery checks, dampers, variable air volume (VAV) boxes, CO₂ and temperature sensors, control calibration, building management system interface, functional testing and documentation.

Replacement costs at the end of component service life were excluded from this maintenance calculation. These costs are conceptually different from routine maintenance and would otherwise overlap with replacement assumptions used in other LCAs. The maintenance indicator therefore represents recurring service costs only, not major refurbishment or end-of-life replacement.

3.6.3 ENERGY COST CALCULATION

Energy costs were calculated as the operational electricity cost associated with the delivered energy demand of each ventilation scenario. The calculation used delivered energy rather than net energy, because delivered energy represents the energy carrier that must be purchased by the building operator. All relevant delivered energy was treated as electricity. The calculation therefore did not differentiate between separate tariffs for district heating, fuels or other energy carriers.

The data basis differed between the scenarios. For the NV scenario, the calculation used the measured delivered energy demand from the office areas of Vertikal Nydalen. This reflects the as-built system in operation and was therefore considered more representative than the pre-construction simulation. For the HV and MV scenarios, no measured energy data exists because both alternatives are hypothetical. Their energy cost estimates were therefore based on the simulated delivered energy demand from Bekkeli (2021), which was also used as the technical reference for the scenario comparison.

The annual energy cost was calculated by multiplying the scenario-specific delivered energy demand by the selected electricity price. The result was expressed as NOK/m²a and used as an operational cost indicator in the economic assessment. This indicator was kept separate from maintenance costs, since it represents purchased energy rather than service work or component upkeep.

3.7 DATA QUALITY, UNCERTAINTY AND SENSITIVITY

The following sections describe how the reliability of the data basis was considered in the evaluation. Since the three ventilation scenarios were not supported by the same type of evidence, data robustness, sensitivity and methodological limitations were assessed separately from the sustainability performance scores.

3.7.1 DATA SOURCES

The evaluation framework was based on several types of data sources, including measured operational data, project-specific documentation, simulations, previous research, benchmark values, cost data and assumptions. The robustness of these sources differed between the nine evaluation criteria and between the three ventilation scenarios. This was therefore considered explicitly when interpreting the results.

The NV scenario had the strongest data basis because it represents the realised solution in Vertikal Nydalen. For this scenario, several indicators could be assessed using measured data, as-built documentation, project-specific information and direct feedback from the building. This increased the reliability of the results, especially for energy demand, energy costs, investment costs, maintenance costs, design aspects and occupant comfort. The data still required interpretation, but it was generally connected to the actual building rather than to a hypothetical model. The HV and MV scenarios had a weaker data basis because they were not built alternatives. Their assessment therefore depended more strongly on simulations, scenario-based design assumptions, previous calculations, benchmarks and comparable sources. This was particularly relevant for energy demand, emissions, ecopoints and costs, where material quantities, system layouts and operational assumptions influenced the results. The MV scenario was partly more robust than the HV scenario for some cost-related aspects, because conventional mechanical systems are better documented in benchmark sources.

To make this difference transparent, each criterion was assigned a data robustness score from 1 to 5. This score did not describe the sustainability performance of the scenario, but the reliability of the underlying data basis. The robustness assessment was therefore used as a methodological support for interpreting the final comparison (see Table 5).

Criteria		Natural	Hybrid	Mechanical	Robustness Data:		
Environment	Energy	LCA based on measured energy and project-specific data	LCA based on simulated energy and hypothetical system quantities	LCA based on simulated energy and hypothetical system quantities	4	2	2
	Emissions	LCA based on measured energy and project-specific data	LCA based on simulated energy and hypothetical system quantities	LCA based on simulated energy and hypothetical system quantities	4	2	2
	Ecopoints	LCA based on measured energy and project-specific data	LCA based on simulated energy and hypothetical system quantities	LCA based on simulated energy and hypothetical system quantities	4	2	2
Social	Occupant comfort	Occupant surveys and QR feedback from the real building	Comparable -building survey data and scenario interpretation	Comparable -building survey data and scenario interpretation	5	2	3
	Design aspects	As-built drawings, BIM -model and project visuals	Scenario-based design comparison from drawings and BIM -model	Scenario-based design comparison from drawings and BIM -model	5	4	4
	Daylight	Project geometry and daylight simulation	Modified ceiling -height scenario and daylight simulation	Modified ceiling -height scenario and daylight simulation	4	3	3
Economy	Investment costs	Project-specific cost data	Benchmarks and reports	Benchmarks, reports and Norsk Prisbok	5	3	4
	Maintenance costs	Project-specific maintenance basis	Benchmarks and supplier -related assumptions	Benchmarks and supplier -related assumptions	5	3	4
	Energy costs	Based on measured energy and local electricity price	Based on measured energy and local electricity price	Based on measured energy and local electricity price	5	2	2

Table 5 Reliability assessment of data sources

3.7.2 SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to test whether selected assumptions had a significant influence on the results. The analysis focused on parameters that were considered both uncertain and influential for the final environmental assessment. Three aspects were selected: delivered energy demand, electricity emission factor and ecopoint weighting.

Delivered energy demand was included because it directly affects operational energy use, GHG emissions, ecopoints and energy costs. It is also a central uncertainty because the NV scenario was based on measured operational data, while the HV and MV scenarios were based on hypothetical or previously simulated values. By varying the delivered energy demand, the analysis tested whether the relative performance of the scenarios remained stable under higher or lower operational demand.

The electricity emission factor was included because the climate impact of operational energy depends strongly on the assumed electricity mix. This is especially relevant in Norway, where a low-carbon electricity mix can reduce the relative importance of operational emissions compared with embodied impacts. Testing alternative emission factors therefore helped to identify whether the environmental ranking was dependent on the selected electricity scenario.

Ecopoint weighting was included because the ecopoint method combines several environmental impact categories into one aggregated score. Since weighting always involves methodological choices, the sensitivity analysis tested how changes in weighting affected the overall environmental interpretation. The aim was not to replace the base results, but to evaluate whether small changes in key assumptions could shift the ranking between NV, HV and MV.

3.7.3 LIMITATIONS AND UNCERTAINTY

The methodological used in this study has several limitations that are important to take into account when interpreting the results. First, the 1–5 scoring system is not based on a certified assessment standard. It was developed as a comparative tool for this thesis and is intended to provide a clear overview of relative performance across different sustainability aspects. The scores should therefore not be understood as absolute performance values or as a formal certification result. Second, the three ventilation scenarios were not supported by the same level of data quality. The NV scenario represents the realised building and could therefore be assessed with more project-specific information. The HV and MV scenarios were hypothetical alternatives, which means that their results depend more strongly on assumptions regarding system layout, material quantities, control logic, cost levels and operation. Third, several indicators required simplifications. Cost estimates were based partly on benchmarks and may not fully reflect project-specific procurement conditions. Environmental results depend on selected LCA datasets, electricity factors and weighting choices. Daylight and design aspects were assessed through scenario-based modifications rather than detailed design development. Occupant comfort was also difficult to compare directly, because measured user feedback was available mainly for the realised NV scenario. Finally, the framework gives equal importance to all nine criteria unless otherwise stated. This improves transparency, but it does not represent the priorities of all stakeholders. The results should therefore be interpreted as a structured comparison within the defined thesis boundary, not as a universally valid ranking of ventilation systems.

4 RESULTS

The results are presented for the three sustainability dimensions used in the evaluation framework. In Chapters 4.1–4.3, each main chapter first presents the summarised assessment of NV, HV and MV. The following sub-chapters then show the more detailed results that formed the basis for this assessment.

4.1 ENVIRONMENTAL RESULTS

The environmental results shown in Figure 16 summarises the relative performance of NV, HV and MV across primary energy, GHG emissions and ecopoints. NV showed the strongest overall environmental performance in the chart. This was mainly related to its lower operational energy demand and reduced amount of ventilation-related technical components. HV performed between the other two scenarios. It reduced part of the technical and operational impact compared with MV but still required more equipment and energy input than the NV scenario. MV showed the weakest environmental performance, especially because of higher operational energy demand and greater material intensity. The three criteria therefore showed a consistent trend, although the underlying causes differed between energy use, climate impact and broader ecopoint-weighted environmental effects.

Figure 16 Environmental performance of ventilation scenarios

4.1.1 ENERGY

The primary energy results showed clear differences between the three ventilation scenarios. NV had the lowest total primary energy demand, followed by HV, while MV had the highest demand. As shown in the Figure 17, the total primary energy demand was approximately 280 MWh for NV, about 520 MWh for HV and about 670 MWh for MV. The MV scenario therefore required more than twice as much primary energy as the NV scenario, while HV was positioned between the two alternatives.

The main difference between the scenarios was caused by operational energy use rather than embodied primary energy in the technical materials. The embodied contribution from materials and replacements was visible, especially for HV and MV, but it remained smaller than the operational contribution. This reflects the defined system boundary, where all delivered energy categories influenced by the ventilation principle were considered. These included space heating, ventilation heating, space cooling, ventilation cooling, fans and pumps. Within this boundary, the ventilation-related delivered energy demand was 5.5 kWh/m²a for NV, 10.1 kWh/m²a for HV and 13.0 kWh/m²a for MV. NV was therefore approximately 46% lower than HV and approximately 58% lower than MV. The result also reflects that NV did not require continuous fan-driven air supply. However, it still influenced heating and cooling demand through façade openings and the LowEx system. For this reason, the assessment did not isolate fan energy only, but included all energy demand linked to the ventilation strategy.

NV received 4 points because it had the lowest primary energy demand but still caused operational energy use and material-related impacts. HV received 2 points because it reduced the demand compared with MV

but remained substantially above NV. MV received 1 point because it had the highest primary energy demand and the largest operational contribution.

Figure 17 Primary energy through the life cycle of ventilation scenarios

4.1.2 EMISSIONS

The GHG emission results followed the same overall ranking with NV having the lowest total emissions, followed by HV, while MV had the highest emissions. As shown in the Figure 18, the total result was approximately 7,500 kg CO₂eq for NV, around 19,500 kg CO₂eq for HV and around 28,500 kg CO₂eq for MV. HV therefore had more than twice the emissions of NV, while MV had almost four times the emissions of NV within the assessed boundary.

The distribution of emissions between the considered LCA stages was more even than in the primary energy result. Product stage emissions, replacements and operational energy use all contributed visibly to the total result. This indicates that material quantities and component replacements played a more important role for GHG emissions than for primary energy. NV required fewer ventilation-related technical components than the hybrid and mechanical alternatives, which reduced its material-related emissions. At the same time, because the material impact was lower, operational emissions represented a larger share of the total for NV than for the more material-intensive alternatives. HV showed an intermediate result because it combined façade-integrated NV components with a reduced mechanical system. This increased material-related emissions compared with NV, but kept the technical scope below that of MV. MV had the highest result because it required the most extensive technical infrastructure, including air-handling equipment, ducts, valves, dampers and control components.

NV received 4 points because it achieved the lowest GHG emissions, although the result was not impact-free due to remaining operational and material-related emissions. HV received 2 points because it reduced emissions compared with MV but remained clearly above NV. MV received 1 point because it had the highest total emissions across the assessed life-cycle stages.

Greenhouse Gas Emissions

Figure 18 Life cycle greenhouse gas emissions of ventilation scenarios

4.1.3 ECOPOINTS

The ecopoint results showed the broader environmental impact of the ventilation scenarios beyond climate change alone. NV achieved the lowest ecopoint score, followed by HV, while MV had the highest score. As shown in the Figure 19, the total result was approximately 1.3 ecopoints for NV, 4.2 ecopoints for HV and 6.2 ecopoints for MV. The MV scenario therefore had almost five times the ecopoint result of NV, while HV had more than three times the impact of NV.

The internal distribution differed from the GHG results. Resource depletion of minerals and metals was the dominant impact category and accounted for around two thirds of the total ecopoint result. This indicates that material extraction and the use of metal-intensive technical components had a major influence on the aggregated score. The effect was strongest for MV, where ducts, air-handling equipment, dampers, valves and other technical components increased material-related impacts. HV also showed a substantial contribution from this category, but the reduced mechanical scope kept the total impact below the MV scenario. Climate change represented only a small share of the ecopoint result, with a contribution of only a few percent. This differs from the GHG assessment, where climate change was the central indicator. The ecopoint results therefore showed that conclusions based only on GHG emissions would not fully capture the environmental relevance of resource use and material intensity.

NV received 5 points because it performed clearly best and showed a large distance to both alternative scenarios. HV received 2 points because it reduced the ecopoint result compared with MV, but still had a substantially higher impact than NV. MV received 1 point because it had the highest ecopoint score and the strongest contribution from mineral and metal resource depletion.

Figure 19 Life cycle ecopoints of ventilation scenarios

4.2 SOCIAL RESULTS

The social results were assessed through occupant comfort, design aspects and daylight performance. The spider chart in Figure 20 shows that the NV scenario achieved the strongest overall social profile, followed by HV, while MV showed the lowest performance across the assessed criteria. The difference was mainly related to the combined effect of user satisfaction, spatial quality and daylight-related design potential.

NV performed strongest because the as-built office spaces in Vertikal Nydalen showed high reported satisfaction with the indoor climate and retained an open ceiling without visible ductwork. The façade-integrated ventilation openings also offered additional daylight potential when considered as transparent elements. HV showed an intermediate result. It retained some qualities of the natural concept, but the added ductwork reduced the architectural calmness of the space. MV performed lowest in the social assessment. Although it can provide stable technical control of IAQ and temperature, the required ductwork and larger ceiling reductions had a stronger spatial impact. The chart therefore indicates that the social performance was not determined by comfort alone, but by the combined interaction between perceived indoor climate, architectural integration and daylight conditions.

Figure 20 Social performance of ventilation scenarios

4.2.1 OCCUPANT COMFORT

The occupant comfort results showed clear differences between the compared ventilation scenarios. As shown in the Figure 21, Vertikal Nydalen had the highest indoor climate satisfaction among the assessed buildings. The naturally ventilated case reached an average satisfaction value of approximately 1.1, while the hybrid reference building, Powerhouse Montessori in Sandvika, reached approximately 0.75. The mechanically ventilated reference building, Nydalsveien 28 in Oslo, had the lowest value, at approximately 0.6. The results therefore indicate that the naturally ventilated office spaces in Vertikal Nydalen were perceived more positively than the two comparison cases. The temperature dissatisfaction results showed a similar tendency. In Vertikal Nydalen, only around 8% of respondents were dissatisfied with temperature. The hybrid reference case showed a higher share, at approximately 17%, while the mechanically ventilated reference case had the highest share of dissatisfied occupants, at approximately 29%. This result is notable because the NV concept supplies outdoor air directly through façade openings, which may create cold-air entry and draught risks in a Nordic winter climate. Despite this technical risk, occupants in the naturally ventilated spaces were the least dissatisfied with temperature.

Overall, the survey-based results showed that the realised NV scenario achieved the strongest occupant comfort performance. The result does not mean that NV eliminates all indoor climate risks, since previous technical analysis identified potential challenges related to cold periods, draught and CO₂ control. However, within the available post-occupancy feedback, occupants in Vertikal Nydalen reported the highest satisfaction with the indoor climate in general. Therefore, NV got 4 points in this category. HV was rated 2 points. The result was based on the intermediate reference performance, where temperature dissatisfaction was higher than in Vertikal Nydalen but lower than in the mechanical reference. The score also reflected that HV can improve robustness through mechanical support, but the available occupant feedback did not show the same level of satisfaction as the realised NV case. MV was rated 1 point. Although mechanical systems generally provide more controllable airflow and stable operation, the reference result showed the lowest indoor climate satisfaction and the highest temperature dissatisfaction. Within this comparative assessment, the MV scenario therefore performed weakest for occupant comfort.

Figure 21 Occupant comfort performance of ventilation scenarios

4.2.2 DESIGN ASPECTS

The design assessment in Figure 22 and Figure 23 showed that the ventilation principle affected the spatial character of the office areas in several ways. As visualised in the renders, the NV scenario kept the ceiling open and avoided visible supply ductwork in the room. This created a calmer visual expression and preserved the architectural quality of the exposed ceiling. The open ceiling also strengthened the perception of height and material depth in the space. The absence of visible ducts made the room appear less technically occupied and allowed the architectural elements to dominate the visual impression.

The HV and MV scenarios were assessed in two spatial variants. In the lowered-ceiling variants, the technical installations were hidden above a suspended ceiling. This produced a clean and controlled interior appearance, but it also reduced the spatial quality created by the exposed ceiling. The ceiling reduction was smaller for HV, where a 30 cm lowered ceiling was assumed because the reduced airflow required smaller ducts. In the MV scenario, a 60 cm lowered ceiling was assumed because the higher airflow demand and larger duct dimensions required more space. The renders showed that this reduction changed the room proportions more strongly in the MV scenario than in the HV scenario. The lowered-ceiling variant therefore appeared more spatially compressed, although it had a visually clean surface.

The open-ceiling variants for HV and MV showed a different design consequence. In these variants, the original ceiling height and the quality of the exposed structure could partly be retained. However, the visible ductwork and technical components made the ceiling zone visually busier. This effect was stronger in the MV scenario because the duct dimensions and system extent were larger. HV had a more limited technical presence, but the visible ducts still reduced the visual calmness compared with the NV scenario. The NV scenario also showed an additional design potential through the façade openings. The opaque opening variant maintained the as-built character, while the transparent variant indicated that the high-level ventilation openings could admit additional daylight into deeper parts of the room. Because the openings were placed high in the façade, they had the potential to direct daylight further into the office area than lower window openings alone. This effect was evaluated as a design-related quality, even though the transparent variant represented an experimental option rather than the realised solution.

NV was rated 4 points because it preserved the open ceiling, avoided visible ductwork and offered additional façade-integrated design potential. It did not receive 5 points because the ventilation openings still form a specific architectural and technical element that may not be equally suitable in all spatial contexts. HV was rated 3 points because it retained some architectural flexibility and required less duct space than MV but still introduced visible or concealed technical infrastructure. MV was rated 2 points because it provided the least favourable spatial result, mainly due to larger ducts, a greater ceiling reduction or a more visually dominant open technical installation. Larger versions of the renderings can be found in Appendix E-J.

Natural Ventilation
(opaque openings)

Hybrid Ventilation
(lowered ceiling)

Mechanical Ventilation
(lowered ceiling)

Figure 22 3D Visualisations of ventilation scenarios (Part 1)

Natural Ventilation
(transparent openings)

Hybrid Ventilation
(open ceiling)

Mechanical Ventilation
(open ceiling)

Figure 23 3D visualisations of ventilation scenarios (Part 2)

4.2.3 DAYLIGHT

The daylight results showed only limited differences between the ventilation scenarios when the façade openings remained opaque. The daylight factor and illuminance distributions shown in Figure 24 were mainly controlled by the existing façade geometry, room depth and window arrangement rather than by the ventilation system itself. The highest values occurred along the façade zones, while the deeper office areas remained noticeably lower in both daylight factor and illuminance. This pattern was visible across all scenarios and confirmed that the main daylight gradient was caused by distance from the external glazing.

The lowered ceiling variants for HV and MV did not show a significant difference compared with the open-ceiling reference. The 30 cm ceiling reduction in the HV scenario and the 60 cm ceiling reduction in the MV scenario had only a minor visible effect on the daylight factor and illuminance results. This indicates that, within the tested model boundary, the reduced ceiling height affected spatial perception more strongly than measurable daylight availability. The results therefore did not support a major daylight penalty from the lowered ceilings alone.

A visible difference was only observed in the hypothetical transparent ventilation openings. In the NV scenario, the transparent high-level openings increased daylight access near the façade and helped bring more light into areas further away from the main windows. This effect was less related to the ventilation principle itself and more to the additional light-transmitting façade area. The transparent opening variant

was experimental and did not represent the realised solution at Vertikal Nydalen, where the openings include sound-insulating layers. The thesis methodology also defined the daylight analysis as a relative comparison of ventilation-related design changes, not as a full daylight certification study.

NV was rated 4 points because it achieved daylight performance comparable to the other scenarios and showed additional potential through transparent high-level openings. HV was also rated 4 points because the reduced ceiling height did not substantially reduce daylight availability. MV was rated 3 points because its daylight result was still acceptable, but the larger ceiling reduction and stronger spatial impact provided less architectural daylight potential than the other two scenarios.

Figure 24 Illuminance and daylight factor performance of ventilation scenarios

4.3 ECONOMIC RESULTS

The economic results compare the three ventilation scenarios based on investment costs, maintenance costs and energy costs. Figure 25 summarises the assessment scores and shows a clear gradient between the scenarios. NV achieved the strongest economic profile, with high scores in all three criteria. This reflected the lower initial cost of the realised façade-integrated system, the comparatively low routine maintenance cost and the substantially lower operational energy cost. HV showed an intermediate but clearly reduced economic performance. It benefited from a smaller mechanical system than the fully mechanical alternative but still required both automated openings and MV components. This increased investment and maintenance costs compared with NV. MV received the lowest economic assessment. Its cost profile was affected by the largest technical installation, higher maintenance requirements and the highest energy cost. The chart therefore indicates that increasing technical complexity was associated with higher cost levels across all assessed economic criteria.

Figure 25 Economic performance of ventilation scenarios

4.3.1 INVESTMENT COSTS

The investment cost results showed a clear cost increase from NV to HV and MV (see Figure 26). Based on the collected cost values, the NV scenario had the lowest average investment cost, at 816 NOK/m². The HV scenario increased to 1,359 NOK/m², while the MV scenario reached 1,673 NOK/m². NV was therefore approximately 40% lower than HV and 50% lower than MV. HV was approximately 19% lower than MV, which reflected the reduced mechanical system size, but also the additional cost of automated NV components.

The individual source values also showed different levels of variation. For NV, the values ranged from 682 to 1,050 NOK/m². The actual investment cost of the NV system in Vertikal Nydalen was within this range and correlated with other sources for NV systems. This supported the plausibility of the case-specific value, although it remained dependent on system scope and project-specific integration. For the HV and MV scenarios, the values were derived from hypothetical alternatives and comparable benchmark sources. The HV values ranged from 1,326 to 1,400 NOK/m², while the mechanical values ranged from 1,510 to 1,760 NOK/m². These sources therefore indicated a similar cost range within each scenario and supported the overall ranking.

The assessment followed the grading method described in the methodology, where lower investment cost represented better economic performance. NV received 4 points because it had the lowest cost level, but was not assigned the maximum score due to remaining uncertainty in cost scope and project-specific integration. HV received 2 points because it was clearly more expensive than NV, although still below the mechanical alternative. MV received 1 point because it had the highest average investment cost and the largest technical installation scope.

Investment Costs

Figure 26 Investment costs of ventilation scenarios

4.3.2 MAINTENANCE COSTS

The maintenance cost results showed the same overall ranking as the investment cost results, but with larger uncertainty between sources (see Figure 27). Based on the collected annual cost values, NV had the lowest average maintenance cost, at 36 NOK/m²a. HV increased to 59 NOK/m²a, while MV reached 84 NOK/m²a. NV was therefore approximately 39% lower than HV and 57% lower than MV. HV was approximately 30% lower than MV.

The source range was considerable. For NV, the values ranged from 16 to 61 NOK/m²a. The actual maintenance costs for Vertikal Nydalen were much lower than several of the other identified sources, which indicated that the realised system may have a particularly favourable maintenance agreement or a narrower service scope than broader benchmark values. For HV, the identified values ranged from 40.5 to 73 NOK/m²a. This reflected the combined maintenance of automated openings, sensors and controls with a reduced mechanical system. For MV, the range was even wider, from 45 to 121 NOK/m²a, showing that maintenance assumptions for AHUs, filters, fans, controls and inspection routines can vary substantially between sources and scopes.

The assessment was based on the average cost level, while acknowledging this uncertainty. NV received 4 points because it had the lowest maintenance cost, but not the maximum score because the source range and service boundaries were not fully consistent. HV received 3 points because it was still above NV and required more technical maintenance. MV received 1 point because it had the highest average maintenance cost and the most extensive recurring service scope.

Maintenance Costs

Figure 27 Maintenance costs of different ventilation scenarios

4.3.3 ENERGY COSTS

The energy cost results showed the clearest economic difference between the three scenarios. As shown in Figure 28, NV had an annual energy cost of approximately 9.7 NOK/m²a. HV had a cost of about 19.5 NOK/m²a, while MV reached approximately 25.1 NOK/m²a. The NV scenario was therefore around 50% lower than the HV scenario and around 60% lower than the MV scenario. HV was approximately 22% lower than MV.

The ranking reflected the delivered energy demand used as the basis for the energy cost calculation. NV required less purchased energy because the ventilation concept reduced fan energy and used the building design more directly for air exchange. The HV scenario reduced part of the demand compared with MV, but still included mechanical air supply and associated operation. MV had the highest cost because it relied most strongly on mechanical air transport and technical conditioning during operation. However, the evidence basis differed between the scenarios. The NV value was based on measured data from the realised office areas in Vertikal Nydalen. In contrast, the hybrid and mechanical values were based on simulated scenario data from the previous study. The comparison therefore combined measured operational performance for the as-built case with simulated values for the two hypothetical alternatives. This did not change the observed ranking, but it limited the direct comparability of the absolute cost values.

The assessment followed the same lower-is-better principle as the other economic criteria. NV received 4 points because it showed the lowest energy cost by a large margin but was not assigned 5 points due to the

mixed data basis and remaining operational uncertainty. HV received 2 points because it was clearly more costly than NV, although lower than MV. It received 1 point because it had the highest annual energy cost.

Figure 28 Energy cost of different ventilation scenarios

4.4 COMPARATIVE SUMMARY

The comparative summary brings together the results from the nine evaluated criteria and shows the overall performance of the three ventilation scenarios within the defined assessment framework. Figure 29 presents the individual scores for primary energy, GHG emissions, ecopoints, occupant comfort, design aspects, daylight, investment costs, maintenance costs and energy costs. The chart shows a clear difference between the scenarios.

NV achieved the most comprehensive and balanced performance across the nine assessment criteria and performed very well in all three dimensions of sustainability. It achieved the best results in the environmental and economic categories, where it recorded the lowest primary energy consumption, the lowest GHG emissions, and the lowest investment, maintenance and energy costs. NV also performed well in the social criteria, primarily because the implemented solution retained the open ceiling, avoided exposed pipework and achieved a high level of user satisfaction.

HV showed an intermediate profile in the spider chart. It performed better than MV in most criteria but did not reach the same level as NV. The HV scenario benefited from a reduced mechanical system compared with the fully mechanical alternative, but it still required technical infrastructure in addition to the façade-integrated NV components. This increased material use, cost and spatial impact compared with the NV scenario. Its strongest relative result was found in daylight, where the lowered ceiling did not substantially reduce the daylight performance. However, the HV scenario scored lower in environmental and economic criteria because its operational energy demand, emissions and costs remained clearly above the NV case.

MV showed the smallest overall profile in the spider chart. It received the lowest scores in the environmental and economic criteria and also performed weaker in the social assessment. The scenario had the highest technical complexity, the largest material input, the highest energy cost and the strongest spatial consequences due to ductwork and ceiling reduction. Although MV can provide stable technical control of airflow and indoor climate, this advantage was not reflected as a dominant result within the final multi-criteria assessment.

Figure 29 Overall performance of ventilation scenarios

The triangular chart condenses the nine criteria into the three main sustainability dimensions: environmental, social and economic performance. Each dimension represents the combined score of its three underlying indicators. In this summary, NV achieved the strongest final profile, with approximately 4 points for environmental performance, 4 points for social performance and 4 points for economic performance. HV formed the intermediate result, with approximately 2 points for environmental performance, 3 points for social performance and 2 points for economic performance. MV achieved the lowest final profile, with approximately 1 point for environmental performance, 2 points for social performance and 1.0 point for economic performance.

Overall, the final results in Figure 30 show that the NV scenario achieved the most favourable holistic sustainability performance. HV represented a middle position, while MV performed lowest in the combined assessment. These results should be understood as comparative and case-specific, since they depend on the selected criteria, equal weighting approach, available data sources and the particular design conditions of Vertikal Nydalen.

Figure 30 Final sustainability performance of ventilation scenarios

5 DISCUSSION

The results show that the three ventilation strategies cannot be judged by one factor alone. Natural ventilation performed best in the overall assessment, hybrid ventilation was placed in the middle, and mechanical ventilation received the lowest score. However, this result should not be read too generally. It is linked to the specific case of Vertikal Nydalen, the selected indicators and the available data. The natural ventilation scenario is the realised building and is supported by measured data and project-specific feedback. The hybrid and mechanical scenarios are hypothetical alternatives and are therefore more dependent on assumptions, previous simulations and benchmark values.

For this reason, the discussion does not only focus on which system performed best. It also looks at why this result occurred, where the findings are strong, and where uncertainty remains. This is important because ventilation systems are closely linked to architecture, energy use, comfort, material use and cost. A system that performs well in one building may not perform equally well in another.

5.1 ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE

The environmental results indicate that the NV scenario performed best across primary energy demand, GHG emissions and ecopoints. This finding is consistent with the main logic of the study. Reducing mechanical air transport, ductwork and air-handling infrastructure can lower both operational and embodied environmental impacts. The result also supports earlier findings by Bekkeli (2021), who found that NV and HV reduced delivered energy demand and GHG emissions compared with a fully mechanical alternative in Vertikal Nydalen. In the present thesis, the conclusion is strengthened by the use of measured operational energy data for the as-built NV scenario, which showed substantially lower ventilation-related delivered energy demand than the hybrid and mechanical alternatives.

The primary energy result was mostly influenced by operational energy. Natural ventilation required less energy because it avoided continuous fan-driven air supply. Instead, airflow is mainly created through the building form, façade openings and control logic. This shows that reduced fan energy can be important in Nordic office buildings. At the same time, the result does not mean that natural ventilation is always the best low-energy solution. In cold climates, mechanical ventilation with efficient heat recovery can also reduce heating losses. Laverge and Janssens (2012) say that the benefit of heat recovery depends on climate, system efficiency and primary energy factors. Fan energy, pressure losses and real operation can reduce this benefit. In Vertikal Nydalen, the natural ventilation strategy seems to have achieved a good balance between low fan energy and acceptable heating demand.

The GHG emission results followed the same ranking, but the underlying causes were more balanced between operational energy, product stage emissions and replacements. This is important because it shows that ventilation-related environmental performance cannot be assessed only through operational energy. MV had the highest emissions because it combined higher energy demand with the largest material inventory. This is consistent with Kiamili et al. (2020), who demonstrate that HVAC systems can represent a substantial share of embodied carbon in office buildings. Bergsdal et al. (2024) and Liu et al. (2024) further show that ducts, fittings and ventilation components have relevant embodied impacts and should be included when comparing system alternatives. The present results therefore support the argument that technical complexity itself can become an environmental burden, especially when larger ducts, AHUs, dampers, valves, controls and replacements are required.

The ecopoint result adds an important critical perspective because climate change represented only a small share of the aggregated score, while resource depletion of minerals and metals dominated. This means that a GHG-only comparison would not fully describe the environmental consequences of the ventilation strategies. The MV scenario performed worst not only because of higher emissions, but also because it required more metal-intensive technical components. This strengthens the relevance of including broader environmental indicators in ventilation assessment. It also shows why simplified technical systems can have environmental value beyond energy savings alone. At the same time, the ecopoint method used in this thesis

was based on a reduced set of available impact categories and should not be interpreted as a complete Environmental Footprint score. The ecopoint results are therefore useful for relative comparison within the thesis boundary, but not as an absolute environmental classification.

5.2 SOCIAL PERFORMANCE

NV had the strongest performance across occupant comfort, design aspects and daylight. This is a relevant finding because previous technical assessments of NV in cold climates often highlight risks related to draught, low winter temperatures, elevated CO₂ levels and overheating (Bekkeli, 2021). The post-occupancy feedback used in this thesis showed a more positive picture for the realised NV scenario than these risks alone would suggest. Occupants in Vertikal Nydalen reported high indoor climate satisfaction and relatively low temperature dissatisfaction compared with the hybrid and mechanical reference cases. This indicates that the as-built NV concept was not only environmentally favourable but also perceived positively by users. Nevertheless, the comfort result must be interpreted carefully. The comfort comparison was not based on identical survey designs, identical buildings or identical occupant groups. The NV case was supported by case-specific feedback from Vertikal Nydalen, while the hybrid and mechanical cases were supported by reference buildings and literature. This makes the comfort assessment less statistically robust than the environmental calculations. It is therefore more appropriate to interpret the result as a comparative tendency than as proof that NV generally provides better comfort than HV or MV. Studies by Gupta and Howard (2020) and Hummelgaard et al. (2007) also show that perceived indoor environmental quality does not always follow the same pattern as measured technical performance. Occupants may value factors such as perceived control, freshness, connection to outside air and spatial quality, which are not fully captured by temperature or CO₂ values.

The design assessment strongly favoured the NV scenario because the as-built solution avoided visible supply ductwork and preserved the open ceiling. This result is central to the architectural relevance of the study. NV was not only a technical system but part of the spatial concept of Vertikal Nydalen. By reducing duct space and allowing the ceiling to remain open, the system supported room height, visual calmness and architectural clarity. The MV scenario showed the strongest spatial impact because it required either visible ductwork or a larger lowered ceiling. HV reduced this impact compared with MV, but still introduced technical infrastructure that weakened the spatial quality compared with the natural scenario.

The daylight results showed only limited differences between the opaque ventilation scenarios. This suggests that daylight performance was mainly controlled by façade geometry, room depth and window arrangement, rather than by the ventilation system itself. The lowered ceilings in the HV and MV scenarios had only minor effects on daylight factor and illuminance within the tested model boundary. The most visible daylight improvement appeared only in the hypothetical transparent opening variant, which was not the realised solution. This means that the daylight benefit of NV should not be overstated. The main social advantage of NV in this study was spatial and experiential rather than a major measurable daylight improvement.

5.3 ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE

The economic results show a clear cost gradient from NV to HV and MV. NV had the lowest investment cost, maintenance cost and energy cost. HV performed better than MV but remained clearly more expensive than NV. MV had the highest costs across all three economic indicators. This ranking reflects the increasing technical complexity of the scenarios. More equipment, larger duct systems, controls, filters, AHUs and service requirements resulted in higher capital and operational cost levels.

The low investment cost of NV supports the assumption that simplified ventilation strategies can reduce initial technical costs when they are integrated into the building concept. HV was more expensive because

it combined automated façade components with a reduced mechanical system. MV required the largest technical installation and therefore had the highest investment cost. This result is consistent with Fong et al. (2017) who show that ventilation alternatives can differ substantially when LCA and LCC are considered together. It also aligns with Kabbara et al. (2023), who demonstrate that air distribution layout and system sizing influence the cost and performance of MV systems.

Maintenance costs followed the same ranking but were more uncertain. NV had the lowest average maintenance cost, but the source range was broad. The actual maintenance cost that were provided by the company WindowMaster A/S for Vertikal Nydalen was lower than several benchmark values. HV required maintenance of both façade-integrated components and mechanical support systems, while MV involved the most extensive recurring service scope, including filters, fans, AHUs, dampers, controls and inspection routines. The ranking is plausible, but the absolute values should be treated with caution because maintenance boundaries vary strongly between sources.

Energy cost showed the clearest economic difference. NV had the lowest energy cost because its measured delivered energy demand was substantially lower than the simulated hybrid and mechanical alternatives. This result is important because it links economic and environmental performance directly. Lower delivered energy demand reduced both energy cost and environmental impact. However, the energy cost comparison also has a methodological weakness. The NV value was based on measured data from the realised building, while the hybrid and mechanical values were based on simulations from the previous study. The comparison therefore combines real operation with hypothetical scenario data. This does not invalidate the ranking, but it reduces the precision of the absolute cost differences.

The economic findings also show that NV may provide value beyond direct cost savings. Lower technical complexity can reduce dependence on specialist maintenance, replacement-intensive components and future operational adjustments. Motuzienė et al. (2024) show that inefficient MV operation can create performance gaps, which may increase energy demand and operating costs. However, NV also depends on a functioning control system, reliable actuators and correct user interaction. If these components fail or are poorly maintained, the economic benefit may be reduced by comfort complaints, manual interventions or later technical retrofits. The economic superiority of NV is therefore strongest when the system is well commissioned, monitored and maintained.

5.4 SENSITIVITY AND LIMITATIONS

The results should be interpreted as a comparative sustainability overview within the defined case study boundary, not as a universally valid ranking of ventilation systems. The broad framework made it possible to compare environmental, social and economic performance together, but it also introduced uncertainty because the indicators were based on different data types and levels of detail. The most important limitation was the unequal data basis between the scenarios. NV represented the realised building and was supported by measured operational data, project documentation and occupant feedback. HV and MV were hypothetical alternatives based on previous simulations, assumptions, benchmark costs and literature. This makes the NV scenario more empirically robust, while the HV and MV scenarios remain more dependent on assumptions about system design, control strategy, material quantities and operation.

Delivered energy demand was a particularly sensitive parameter because it influenced primary energy, GHG emissions, ecopoints and energy costs at the same time. Since NV used measured energy data, while HV and MV relied on simulated values, the absolute differences between scenarios should be interpreted with caution. Real operation may differ from design assumptions, especially in systems with complex controls or occupancy-dependent ventilation. Further uncertainty came from environmental weighting, cost boundaries and social data quality. In the Norwegian context, low-carbon electricity reduced the importance of operational emissions and increased the relative importance of embodied impacts from technical components. With a higher-carbon electricity mix, the ranking could become more dependent on

operational energy demand and heat recovery efficiency. The ecopoint assessment added a broader environmental perspective, but it was based on selected impact categories and weighting factors. Occupant comfort was also difficult to compare directly because case-specific feedback was mainly available for the NV scenario, while the other scenarios relied more on reference data and interpretation. Investment and maintenance costs were sensitive to service scope, procurement conditions and market variation. A further limitation was the 1–5 scoring system. The scale made it possible to combine different indicators into one readable framework, but it also simplified complex results. Small and large performance differences may appear as the same step, depending on the chosen thresholds. The scoring also required qualitative judgement where data were uncertain or not directly comparable. In addition, all indicators were weighted equally, although stakeholders may value energy, emissions, comfort, spatial quality or cost differently.

These limitations do not change the main tendency of the study, but they define how the findings should be used. The results indicate that the as-built NV strategy performed best within the selected case, indicators and assumptions. Further studies with measured data for hybrid and mechanical buildings, longer monitoring periods and alternative weighting methods would be needed to confirm the robustness of this ranking.

6 CONCLUSION

This thesis evaluated how NV, HV and MV strategies perform from a holistic sustainability perspective in the context of Nordic office building design. Vertikal Nydalen was used as the case study because its office areas apply an as-built NV concept in a cold-climate urban setting. The comparison combined environmental, social and economic indicators in order to assess ventilation strategy beyond energy performance alone.

6.1 KEY FINDINGS

The study showed that the as-built NV scenario achieved the strongest overall sustainability performance. It performed best in the environmental assessment because it had the lowest primary energy demand, GHG emissions and ecopoint result. This was mainly linked to reduced fan-driven air transport, lower operational energy demand and less material-intensive technical infrastructure. The results also showed that the environmental benefit of NV was not limited to climate impact. The ecopoint assessment highlighted that resource depletion from mineral and metal use was an important factor, especially for the more technically intensive hybrid and mechanical systems.

NV also achieved the strongest social performance in the assessment. The as-built solution preserved the open ceiling, avoided visible supply ductwork and supported the architectural concept of Vertikal Nydalen. Occupant feedback further indicated high satisfaction with the indoor environment, despite the comfort risks that are often associated with NV in cold climates. However, the daylight assessment showed only minor differences between the opaque ventilation scenarios. The social advantage of NV was therefore mainly related to spatial quality, architectural integration and perceived comfort, rather than a major measurable daylight improvement.

The economic assessment showed the same overall tendency. NV had the lowest investment cost, maintenance cost and energy cost. HV formed an intermediate solution, while MV had the highest cost level across all three economic indicators. This indicates that reduced technical complexity can provide economic benefits when the ventilation concept is integrated into the architectural design from the beginning.

The results suggest that NV can be a suitable sustainability strategy for Nordic office buildings when climate, building form, façade design and control logic are carefully coordinated. However, the findings should not be interpreted as evidence that MV systems are generally unfavourable or inappropriate. Mechanical systems can provide reliable airflow control, filtration, heat recovery and indoor climate stability, which may be essential in many buildings and site conditions. Their low score in this study was a result of the selected 1–5 evaluation scale, the defined case study boundary and the specific assumptions applied to Vertikal Nydalen. In particular, the MV scenario was assessed against an as-built NV concept that was already highly integrated into the architecture and supported by measured operational data.

The results therefore show that NV performed best in this specific case, not that it is universally superior. Each project must be evaluated individually, considering climate, building geometry, occupancy, façade constraints, noise, pollution, user needs, cost structure and operational strategy. Especially noise and outdoor air pollution can limit the use of NV in building project. The findings from one case study can inform future design decisions, but they cannot be transferred directly to all other office buildings or ventilation projects.

6.2 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Further research should apply the evaluation framework developed in this thesis to additional Nordic office buildings. Vertikal Nydalen represents a highly specific case, where NV was integrated into the architectural concept from the beginning. Other buildings may have different floor depths, façade exposure, acoustic constraints, pollution levels, internal loads and user patterns. Applying the same environmental, social and

economic indicators to several case studies would make it possible to test whether the findings from Vertikal Nydalen are transferable, or whether they are mainly linked to this particular building concept.

A stronger empirical basis is also needed for comparing the three ventilation strategies with the same data quality. In this thesis, the NV scenario was supported by measured operational data and case-specific occupant feedback, while the hybrid and mechanical alternatives were hypothetical scenarios based on simulations, assumptions and benchmark values. Future research should therefore include real office buildings with HV and MV as comparison cases. Evaluating realised projects with measured energy use, documented system layouts, actual maintenance data and occupant feedback would create a more reliable database than hypothetical scenarios alone. This would make it possible to compare NV, HV and MV under more equal evidence conditions and reduce the uncertainty caused by comparing an as-built case with simulated alternatives. Long-term monitoring should be expanded over several years and seasons. Future studies should combine measured energy use, indoor temperature, CO₂ concentration, humidity, air velocity, window-opening behaviour, control signals and occupancy data. This would make it possible to evaluate how NV and HV systems perform during cold winter periods, warm summer periods, shoulder seasons and periods with variable occupancy. Such monitoring would also help identify whether performance remains stable over time or depends strongly on commissioning, maintenance and user behaviour.

Finally, future studies should test different weighting methods in holistic sustainability assessments. The equal weighting used in this thesis made the comparison transparent, but it does not represent all stakeholder priorities. Alternative weighting scenarios could show how the final ranking changes when environmental impact, occupant comfort, architectural quality, technical robustness or cost are prioritised differently. This would make the framework more useful for real design decisions, where different stakeholders may define sustainability in different ways.

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APPENDIX A: DETAILED LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT DATA FOR NATURAL VENTILATION

Natural Ventilation - LCA Results

Section	Resource	User input	Unit	Total use of primary energy ex. raw materials MJ	Global Warming Potential total kg CO ₂ e	Acidification potential, mol H ⁺ eq.	Eutrophication potential, kg P eq.	Eutrophication aquatic marine kg N eq.	Eutrophication terrestrial mol N eq.	Formation potential of tropospheric ozone kg NMVOC eq.	Abiotic depletion potential for non fossil resources (+A2) kg Sbe	Abiotic depletion potential for fossil resources (+A2) MJ	Naming previous master thesis (Bekkeli, 2021)	Datasource
A1-A3	Plywood panel for interior applications, 596 kg/m ³ , Kryssfiner HPL (Fritzøe Engros AS)	0.32	m ³	10340.47	-16.58	2.66	0.033	0.65	7.43	1.92	0.0042	3420.42		EPD Kryssfiner HPL
A1-A3	Wooden frame topswing window with aluminium cladding, triple glazed, 70.12 kg/unit, 1230 x 1480 mm,	539	kg	17226.17	627.67	5.6	0.029	1.08	11.68	3.7	0.0077	12068.31		EPD NorDan NTech Villa Topswing reversible
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DX51D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	21.2	kg	769.82	58.73	0.16	0.00038	0.045	0.46	0.13	0.00034	595.4	SpirokanaEindab (kg/m)Ø0	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded
A1-A3	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	0.9	kg	70.09	4.06	0.048	0.0003	0.0053	0.15	0.019	0.0035	57.78	Avtreksventil WCTROX KSO Ø0	Calculated average for ventilation and valves
A1-A3	Air handling unit (AHU), 40 kg/unit, 385 m ³ /h, Model 60 (Airfri Oy)	1	unit	3522	216.19	4.05	0.018	0.29	7.43	1.04	0.048	1010		EPD Airfri AHU Model 60
A1-A3	Domestic exhaust fan, Duct diameter: 100 mm, airflow rate: 100 m ³ /h, 0.388 kg/unit, E-EXTRA (SIA EIRC)	2	unit	55.8	2.78	0.014	0.00066	0.0032	0.032	0.012	0.000111	48.2		EPD EEXTRA
A1-A3	Sound-insulated centrifugal duct fan, 19.31 kg/unit, KVK Silent 100 EC (Systemair Sverige AB)	2	unit	1396.61	98.56	1.09	0.0058	0.11	2.9	0.48	0.047	1241.51		EPD KVK Silent 100 EC
A1-A3	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	2.46	kg	146.62	9.12	0.029	0.0003	0.0063	0.067	0.025	0.000093	129.64	OverluftsventilSwegon ORTOØ00	EPD ORTO SOTTO
A1-A3	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	3.24	kg	193.1	12.01	0.038	0.00039	0.0083	0.088	0.033	0.00012	170.75	OverluftsventilSwegon ORTOØ00	EPD ORTO SOTTO
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	9.9	kg	749.43	37.09	0.23	0.0017	0.033	0.43	0.12	0.00069	624.69	LyddemperSwegon CLA (50 cm)Ø00	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
A1-A3	Actuator for natural ventilation system (WindowMaster A/S)	18.2	kg	1676.22	118.64	0.78	0.0002	0.11	1.24	0.35	0.018	1410.5	Windowmaster NV AdvanceWMXØ02	EPD MD-23160-EN
B4-B5	Plywood panel for interior applications, 596 kg/m ³ , Kryssfiner HPL (Fritzøe Engros AS)	0.32	m ³	20824.68	505.76	5.39	0.069	1.32	15.17	3.92	0.033	6982.03		EPD Kryssfiner HPL
B4-B5	Wooden frame topswing window with aluminium cladding, triple glazed, 70.12 kg/unit, 1230 x 1480 mm,	539	kg	17856.06	907.45	5.64	0.03	1.09	11.75	3.72	0.17	12697.89		EPD NorDan NTech Villa Topswing reversible
B4-B5	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	0.9	kg	142.63	9.11	0.097	0.0006	0.011	0.29	0.037	0.0076	117.95	Avtreksventil WCTROX KSO Ø0	Calculated average for ventilation and valves
B4-B5	Air handling unit (AHU), 40 kg/unit, 385 m ³ /h, Model 60 (Airfri Oy)	1	unit	7153.52	439.96	8.11	0.037	0.57	14.87	2.08	0.12	2125.89		EPD Airfri AHU Model 60
B4-B5	Domestic exhaust fan, Duct diameter: 100 mm, airflow rate: 100 m ³ /h, 0.388 kg/unit, E-EXTRA (SIA EIRC)	2	unit	113.72	6.73	0.028	0.0013	0.0063	0.064	0.024	0.00052	98.45		EPD EEXTRA
B4-B5	Sound-insulated centrifugal duct fan, 19.31 kg/unit, KVK Silent 100 EC (Systemair Sverige AB)	2	unit	2898.96	200.21	2.19	0.012	0.23	5.8	0.96	0.12	2585.26		EPD KVK Silent 100 EC
B4-B5	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	2.46	kg	299.97	19.8	0.059	0.00061	0.013	0.14	0.05	0.0018	285.8	OverluftsventilSwegon ORTOØ00	EPD ORTO SOTTO
B4-B5	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	3.24	kg	395.08	26.07	0.077	0.0008	0.017	0.18	0.066	0.0023	350.07	OverluftsventilSwegon ORTOØ00	EPD ORTO SOTTO
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	9.9	kg	1525.97	80.82	0.47	0.0034	0.067	0.87	0.25	0.0078	1275.59	LyddemperSwegon CLA (50 cm)Ø00	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
B4-B5	Actuator for natural ventilation system (WindowMaster A/S)	18.2	kg	5103.41	355.54	2.36	0.00081	0.34	3.72	1.05	0.072	4303.77	Windowmaster NV AdvanceWMXØ02	EPD MD-23160-EN
B6	Electricity, Norway, 2023 (One Click LCA)	2849	kWh	905634.99	3790.32	12.83	0.57	3.17	33.25	9.54	0.0057	44852.95		Country specific electricity mixes based on IEA, OneClickLCA
	Total			998'095.3	7510.0	52.0	0.8	9.2	118.0	29.5	0.7	96'432.9		

APPENDIX B: DETAILED LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT DATA FOR HYBRID VENTILATION

Hybrid Ventilation - LCA Results

Section	Resource	User input Unit	Total use of primary energy ex. raw materials MJ	Global Warming Potential total kg CO ₂ e	Acidification potential, Accumulated mol H ⁺ eq.	Eutrophication fresh water kg P eq.	Eutrophication aquatic marine kg N eq.	Eutrophication terrestrial mol N eq.	Formation potential of tropospheric ozone kg NMVOC eq.	Abiotic depletion potential (ADP-elements) for non-fossil resources (+A2) kg Sbe	Abiotic depletion potential (ADP-fossil fuels) for fossil resources (+A2) MJ	Naming previous master thesis (Bekkeli, 2021)	Datasource
A1-A3	Wooden frame topswing window with aluminium cladding, triple glazed, 70.12 kg/unit, 1230 x 1480 mm,	539 kg	1726.17	627.67	5.6	0.029	1.08	11.68	3.7	0.0077	12068.31	EPD NorDan NTech Villa Topswing reversible	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.25 kg	11.77	0.77	0.0038	0.00018	0.0062	0.0062	0.002	0.000096	8.97	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.3 kg	14.12	0.92	0.0045	0.00021	0.0074	0.0074	0.0024	0.00012	10.77	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.39 kg	18.35	1.2	0.0059	0.00028	0.0096	0.0097	0.0031	0.00015	14	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.4 kg	18.82	1.23	0.006	0.00029	0.0098	0.01	0.0032	0.00015	14.35	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.45 kg	21.18	1.38	0.0068	0.00032	0.011	0.011	0.0036	0.00017	16.15	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.5 kg	23.53	1.53	0.0075	0.00036	0.012	0.012	0.004	0.00019	17.94	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.5 kg	23.53	1.53	0.0075	0.00036	0.012	0.012	0.004	0.00019	17.94	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.52 kg	24.47	1.6	0.0078	0.00037	0.013	0.013	0.0042	0.0002	18.66	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.6 kg	28.24	1.84	0.009	0.00044	0.015	0.015	0.0048	0.00023	21.53	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.69 kg	32.47	2.12	0.01	0.00049	0.017	0.017	0.0055	0.00027	24.76	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.7 kg	32.94	2.15	0.011	0.0005	0.017	0.017	0.0056	0.00027	25.12	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.71 kg	33.41	2.18	0.011	0.00051	0.017	0.018	0.0057	0.00027	25.48	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.72 kg	33.88	2.21	0.011	0.00051	0.018	0.018	0.0058	0.00028	25.84	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	0.9 kg	70.09	4.06	0.048	0.0003	0.0053	0.15	0.019	0.0035	57.78	Calculated average for ventilation and valves	
A1-A3	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	1 kg	77.87	4.51	0.054	0.00033	0.0059	0.16	0.021	0.0039	64.2	Calculated average for ventilation and valves	
A1-A3	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	1.1 kg	229.78	15.67	0.11	0.0024	0.019	0.21	0.058	0.0049	200.44	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
A1-A3	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	1.2 kg	250.67	17.1	0.12	0.0026	0.021	0.23	0.063	0.0053	218.67	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	1.3 kg	61.18	3.99	0.02	0.00093	0.032	0.032	0.01	0.0005	46.65	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	1.3 kg	61.18	3.99	0.02	0.00093	0.032	0.032	0.01	0.0005	46.65	EPD Lindab safe fittings	
A1-A3	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	1.4 kg	292.44	19.95	0.14	0.003	0.024	0.27	0.074	0.0062	255.11	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DX51D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	1.92 kg	69.72	5.32	0.015	0.00034	0.0041	0.042	0.012	0.00031	53.92	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded	
A1-A3	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	4.6 kg	960.89	65.54	0.45	0.0099	0.079	0.89	0.24	0.02	838.22	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
A1-A3	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	4.92 kg	293.23	18.23	0.058	0.0059	0.013	0.13	0.05	0.00019	259.28	EPD ORTO SOTTO	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DX51D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	6.16 kg	223.68	17.06	0.048	0.0011	0.013	0.13	0.039	0.00099	173	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded	
A1-A3	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	8.1 kg	482.76	30.02	0.096	0.0097	0.021	0.22	0.083	0.00031	426.87	EPD ORTO SOTTO	
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	8.5 kg	643.45	31.85	0.2	0.0014	0.029	0.37	0.11	0.00059	536.35	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	9.9 kg	749.43	37.09	0.23	0.0017	0.033	0.43	0.12	0.00069	624.69	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
A1-A3	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	10 kg	2088.89	142.49	0.98	0.022	0.17	1.94	0.53	0.044	1822.22	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	10 kg	757	37.46	0.24	0.0017	0.034	0.44	0.13	0.0007	631	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
A1-A3	Actuator for natural ventilation system (WindowMaster A/S)	18.2 kg	1676.22	118.64	0.78	0.0002	0.11	1.24	0.35	0.018	1410.5	EPD MD-23160-EN	
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	18.9 kg	1430.73	70.81	0.45	0.0032	0.064	0.83	0.24	0.0013	1192.59	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DX51D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	19.48 kg	707.36	53.96	0.15	0.00035	0.04	0.43	0.12	0.00031	547.1	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DX51D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	20.13 kg	730.96	55.77	0.16	0.00036	0.043	0.44	0.13	0.00032	565.35	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DX51D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	32.58 kg	1183.05	90.25	0.25	0.00058	0.069	0.71	0.2	0.00052	915.01	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded	
A1-A3	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	36.5 kg	2673.36	166.64	1.89	0.012	0.21	5.87	0.73	0.15	2272.07	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DX51D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	36.98 kg	1342.82	102.44	0.29	0.00066	0.079	0.81	0.23	0.0006	1038.59	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DX51D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	39.87 kg	1447.76	110.45	0.31	0.00071	0.085	0.87	0.25	0.00064	1119.75	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded	
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DX51D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	44.1 kg	1601.36	122.17	0.34	0.00079	0.094	0.96	0.28	0.00071	1238.55	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded	
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	45.3 kg	3429.21	169.72	1.07	0.0076	0.15	1.98	0.57	0.00032	2858.43	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
A1-A3	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	75 kg	5493.2	342.41	3.89	0.024	0.43	12.07	1.5	0.3	4668.64	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV	
A1-A3	Air handling unit with rotary heat exchanger, 2458 kg/unit, GOLD RX 070/ 080 - SILVER C RX 070/ 080 (Sv)	343 kg	29137.75	2108.78	14.7	0.75	2.35	32.79	7.56	0.081	22702.65	EPD GOLD RX 070/ 080 - SILVER C RX 070/ 080	
B4-B5	Wooden frame topswing window with aluminium cladding, triple glazed, 70.12 kg/unit, 1230 x 1480 mm,	539 kg	17856.06	907.45	5.64	0.03	1.09	11.75	3.72	0.17	12697.89	EPD NorDan NTech Villa Topswing reversible	
B4-B5	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	0.9 kg	142.63	9.11	0.097	0.0006	0.011	0.29	0.037	0.0076	117.95	Calculated average for ventilation and valves	
B4-B5	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	1 kg	158.48	10.12	0.11	0.00066	0.012	0.32	0.041	0.0085	131.06	Calculated average for ventilation and valves	
B4-B5	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	1.1 kg	462.57	32.28	0.22	0.0048	0.038	0.43	0.12	0.01	403.8	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
B4-B5	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	1.2 kg	504.62	35.21	0.24	0.0052	0.041	0.47	0.13	0.011	440.51	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
B4-B5	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	1.4 kg	588.72	41.08	0.28	0.006	0.048	0.54	0.15	0.013	513.93	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
B4-B5	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	4.6 kg	1934.37	134.97	0.9	0.02	0.16	1.79	0.49	0.044	1688.62	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
B4-B5	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	4.92 kg	599.94	39.59	0.12	0.0012	0.025	0.27	0.1	0.0036	531.59	EPD ORTO SOTTO	
B4-B5	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	8.1 kg	987.7	65.18	0.19	0.002	0.042	0.44	0.17	0.0059	875.18	EPD ORTO SOTTO	
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	8.5 kg	1310.17	69.39	0.4	0.0029	0.058	0.75	0.22	0.0067	1095.2	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	9.9 kg	1525.97	80.82	0.47	0.0034	0.067	0.87	0.25	0.0078	1275.59	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
B4-B5	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	10 kg	4205.16	293.41	1.97	0.043	0.34	3.89	1.05	0.095	3670.92	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB	
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	10 kg	1541.38	81.64	0.48	0.0034	0.068	0.88	0.25	0.079	1288.47	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
B4-B5	Actuator for natural ventilation system (WindowMaster A/S)	18.2 kg	5103.41	355.54	2.36	0.00081	0.34	3.72	1.05	0.072	4303.77	EPD MD-23160-EN	
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	18.9 kg	2913.21	154.3	0.9	0.0065	0.13	1.66	0.48	0.015	2435.21	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
B4-B5	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	36.5 kg	5446.65	357.2	3.79	0.024	0.42	11.76	1.46	0.31	4640.77	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV	
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	45.3 kg	6982.46	369.83	2.16	0.015	0.31	3.98	1.15	0.036	5836.78	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm	
B4-B5	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	75 kg	11191.75	733.98	7.79	0.049	0.85	24.17	3.01	0.64	9535.82	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV	
B4-B5	Air handling unit with rotary heat exchanger, 2458 kg/unit, GOLD RX 070/ 080 - SILVER C RX 070/ 080 (Sv)	343 kg	59214.67	4200.48	29.46	1.5	4.7	65.68	15.15	0.38	46313.29	EPD GOLD RX 070/ 080 - SILVER C RX 070/ 080	
B6	Electricity, Norway, 2023 (One Click LCA)	5232 kWh	1663138.74	6960.67	23.55	1.04	5.83	61.06	17.52	0.01	82369.47	Country specific electricity mixes based on IEA, OneClickLCA	
	Total		1'861'517.6	19'547.0	113.9	3.6	19.9	271.2	64.0	2.5	239'259.9		

APPENDIX C: DETAILED LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT DATA FOR MECHANICAL VENTILATION

Mechanical Ventilation - LCA Results

Section	Resource	User input Unit	Total use of primary energy ex. raw materials MJ	Global Warming Potential total kg CO ₂ e	Acidification potential, Accumulated Exceedance mol H ⁺ eq.	Eutrophication n fresh water kg P eq.	Eutrophication aquatic marine kg N eq.	Eutrophication of terrestrial mol N eq.	Formation potential of tropospheric ozone kg NMVOC eq.	Abiotic depletion potential (ADP- elements) for non fossil resources (+A2) kg Sbe	Abiotic depletion potential (ADP- fossil fuels) for fossil resources (+A2) MJ	Naming previous master thesis (Bekkeli, 2021)	Datasource
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.24 kg	11.29	0.74	0.0036	0.000017	0.00059	0.006	0.0019	0.000093	8.61	PåstikkLindab psu160+250	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.44 kg	20.71	1.35	0.0066	0.000031	0.0011	0.011	0.0035	0.00017	15.79	PåstikkLindab psu200+400	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.5 kg	23.53	1.53	0.0075	0.000036	0.0012	0.012	0.004	0.00019	17.94	ReduksjonerLindab psu250+160	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.67 kg	31.53	2.06	0.01	0.000048	0.0016	0.017	0.0054	0.00026	24.04	PåstikkLindab psu250+500	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.68 kg	32	2.09	0.01	0.000049	0.0017	0.017	0.0055	0.00026	24.4	PåstikkLindab psu200+250	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	0.8 kg	37.65	2.45	0.012	0.000057	0.002	0.02	0.0064	0.00031	28.71	PåstikkLindab psu250+250	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	0.9 kg	70.09	4.06	0.048	0.0003	0.0053	0.15	0.019	0.0035	57.78	Avtrekksventil WC/TROX KSO 80	Calculated average for ventilation and valves
A1-A3	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	1 kg	77.87	4.51	0.054	0.00033	0.0059	0.16	0.021	0.0039	64.2	Tiluftsventil kopipromøponor uts-100300	Calculated average for ventilation and valves
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	1.3 kg	61.18	3.99	0.02	0.000093	0.0032	0.032	0.01	0.0005	46.65	ReduksjonerLindab psu100+315	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	1.4 kg	65.88	4.29	0.021	0.0001	0.0034	0.035	0.011	0.00054	50.24	ReduksjonerLindab psu15+250	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	1.42 kg	66.83	4.36	0.021	0.0001	0.0035	0.035	0.011	0.00055	50.96	PåstikkLindab psu250+315	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	1.87 kg	88	5.74	0.028	0.00013	0.0046	0.047	0.015	0.00072	67.11	PåstikkLindab psu100+400	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	2.2 kg	103.53	6.75	0.033	0.00016	0.0054	0.055	0.018	0.00085	78.95	ReduksjonerLindab psu500+400	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	2.6 kg	122.36	7.98	0.039	0.00019	0.0064	0.065	0.021	0.001	93.3	PåstikkLindab psu250+400	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Circular ventilation fittings from galvanized steel and EPDM rubber gasket (Lindab Ventilation AB)	2.6 kg	122.36	7.98	0.039	0.00019	0.0064	0.065	0.021	0.001	93.3	ReduksjonerLindab psu100+250	EPD Lindab safe fittings
A1-A3	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	4.92 kg	293.23	18.23	0.058	0.00059	0.013	0.13	0.05	0.00019	259.28	Overlutsventil Swegon ORTO800	EPD ORTO SOTTO
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	6.3 kg	476.91	23.6	0.15	0.0011	0.021	0.28	0.079	0.00044	397.53	Lyddemper Swegon CLA (50 cm)200	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
A1-A3	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	6.6 kg	1376.67	94.04	0.65	0.014	0.11	1.28	0.35	0.029	1202.67	SonespljeldIndivent DCV-SP250	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB
A1-A3	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	8 kg	585.94	36.52	0.41	0.0026	0.045	0.29	0.16	0.032	497.99	Tiluftsventil TROX Tellus LØV-VAV160	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV
A1-A3	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	8.1 kg	482.76	30.02	0.096	0.00097	0.021	0.22	0.083	0.00031	426.87	Overlutsventil Swegon ORTO500	EPD ORTO SOTTO
A1-A3	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	9.2 kg	1921.78	131.09	0.9	0.02	0.16	1.79	0.48	0.041	1676.44	SonespljeldIndivent DCV-SP315	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	10 kg	757	37.46	0.24	0.0017	0.034	0.44	0.13	0.0007	631	Lyddemper Swegon CLA (50 cm)160	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DXS1D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	15.52 kg	563.56	42.99	0.12	0.00028	0.033	0.34	0.097	0.00025	435.88	SpirokanaLindab (kg/m)200	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	17 kg	1286.9	63.69	0.4	0.0028	0.057	0.74	0.21	0.0012	1072.7	Lyddemper Swegon CLA (50 cm)250	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
A1-A3	Rectangular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, DXS1+Z275 (Ventistål AS)	17.26 kg	640.62	54.71	0.43	0.003	0.073	1.19	0.3	0.016	564.2	Rektangulære kanaler produsert i 0,90mm	EPD Rektangulære kanaler produsert i 0,90mm
A1-A3	Rectangular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, DXS1+Z275 (Ventistål AS)	19.34 kg	717.82	61.31	0.48	0.0034	0.081	1.33	0.34	0.018	632.19	Rektangulære kanaler produsert i 0,90mm	EPD Rektangulære kanaler produsert i 0,90mm
A1-A3	Rectangular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, DXS1+Z275 (Ventistål AS)	19.85 kg	736.75	62.92	0.49	0.0035	0.084	1.36	0.35	0.019	648.86	Rektangulære kanaler produsert i 0,90mm	EPD Rektangulære kanaler produsert i 0,90mm
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DXS1D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	21.02 kg	763.28	58.23	0.16	0.00037	0.045	0.46	0.13	0.00034	590.35	SpirokanaLindab (kg/m)80	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DXS1D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	23.16 kg	840.99	64.16	0.18	0.00041	0.049	0.51	0.14	0.00037	650.45	SpirokanaLindab (kg/m)1315	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded
A1-A3	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	25.4 kg	5305.78	361.92	2.49	0.055	0.44	4.93	1.34	0.11	4628.44	SonespljeldIndivent DCV-SP400	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB
A1-A3	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	30.2 kg	2286.14	113.14	0.72	0.005	0.1	1.32	0.38	0.0021	1905.62	Lyddemper Swegon CLA (50 cm)400	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DXS1D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	35.31 kg	1282.18	97.82	0.27	0.00063	0.075	0.77	0.22	0.00057	991.69	SpirokanaLindab (kg/m)160	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded
A1-A3	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	36 kg	2636.73	164.36	1.87	0.012	0.2	5.79	0.72	0.14	2240.95	Tiluftsventil TROX Tellus LØV-VAV200	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DXS1D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	41.64 kg	1511.03	115.35	0.32	0.00074	0.089	0.91	0.26	0.00067	1189.46	SpirokanaLindab (kg/m)300	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded
A1-A3	Rectangular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, DXS1+Z275 (Ventistål AS)	69.07 kg	2563.59	219.94	1.71	0.012	0.29	4.75	1.21	0.066	2257.76	Rektangulære kanaler produsert i 0,90mm	EPD Rektangulære kanaler produsert i 0,90mm
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DXS1D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	87.05 kg	3169.96	241.15	0.67	0.0015	0.19	1.9	0.54	0.0014	2444.81	SpirokanaLindab (kg/m)400	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded
A1-A3	Circular ventilation ducts from galvanized steel, 125 mm diameter, DXS1D+Z275 grade, 1.41 kg/m, Safe	101.46 kg	3684.22	281.07	0.78	0.0018	0.22	2.22	0.63	0.0016	2849.51	SpirokanaLindab (kg/m)250	EPD Circular ventilation duct, folded
A1-A3	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	110 kg	8056.69	502.2	5.7	0.035	0.62	17.7	2.2	0.44	6847.34	Tiluftsventil TROX Tellus LØV-VAV250	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV
A1-A3	Air handling unit with rotary heat exchanger, 2458 kg/unit, GOLD RX 070/080 - SILVER C RX 070/080 (Su	721 kg	61248.74	4432.75	30.89	1.58	4.93	68.92	15.88	0.17	47721.89	Aggregat Swegon Gold F RX 14	EPD GOLD RX 070/080 - SILVER C RX 070/080
B4-B5	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	0.9 kg	142.63	9.11	0.097	0.0006	0.011	0.29	0.037	0.0076	117.95	Avtrekksventil WC/TROX KSO 80	Calculated average for ventilation and valves
B4-B5	Ventilation and valves, calculated average for Norway (One Click LCA)	1 kg	158.48	10.12	0.11	0.00066	0.012	0.32	0.041	0.0085	131.06	Tiluftsventil kopipromøponor uts-100300	Calculated average for ventilation and valves
B4-B5	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	4.92 kg	599.94	39.59	0.12	0.0012	0.025	0.27	0.1	0.0036	531.59	Overlutsventil Swegon ORTO800	EPD ORTO SOTTO
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	6.3 kg	917.07	51.43	0.3	0.0022	0.043	0.55	0.16	0.005	811.74	Lyddemper Swegon CLA (50 cm)200	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
B4-B5	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	6.6 kg	2775.4	193.65	1.3	0.029	0.23	2.57	0.7	0.063	2422.8	SonespljeldIndivent DCV-SP250	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB
B4-B5	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	8 kg	1193.79	78.29	0.83	0.0052	0.091	0.93	0.26	0.069	1017.15	Tiluftsventil TROX Tellus LØV-VAV160	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV
B4-B5	Steel sound attenuating air transfer unit for airflow between rooms, ORTO, SOTTO (Swegon Group AB)	8.1 kg	987.7	65.18	0.19	0.002	0.042	0.44	0.17	0.0059	875.18	Overlutsventil Swegon ORTO500	EPD ORTO SOTTO
B4-B5	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	9.2 kg	3868.75	269.94	1.81	0.04	0.32	3.58	0.97	0.088	3377.24	SonespljeldIndivent DCV-SP315	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	10 kg	1541.38	81.64	0.48	0.0034	0.068	0.88	0.25	0.0079	1288.47	Lyddemper Swegon CLA (50 cm)160	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	17 kg	2620.35	138.79	0.81	0.0058	0.12	1.49	0.43	0.013	2190.4	Lyddemper Swegon CLA (50 cm)250	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
B4-B5	Airflow control damper for ventilation systems, 4.5 kg/unit, WISE Damper (Swegon Group AB)	25.4 kg	10681.1	745.27	5	0.11	0.87	9.67	2.68	0.24	9324.13	SonespljeldIndivent DCV-SP400	EPD WISE Damper, Swegon Group AB
B4-B5	Flexible ventilation silencer, Diameter: 25 mm, AKUCOMP (REC Indovent AB)	30.2 kg	4854.97	246.55	1.44	0.01	0.2	2.85	0.76	0.024	3891.19	Lyddemper Swegon CLA (50 cm)400	EPD AKUCOMP 25 mm
B4-B5	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	36 kg	5372.04	352.31	3.74	0.023	0.41	11.6	1.44	0.31	4577.19	Tiluftsventil TROX Tellus LØV-VAV200	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV
B4-B5	Circular supply diffuser, 8.45 kg/unit, Tellus-LØV VAV (TROX Auroran AS)	110 kg	16414.56	1076.51	11.43	0.071	1.25	35.44	4.41	0.95	13985.87	Tiluftsventil TROX Tellus LØV-VAV250	EPD Tellus-LØV VAV
B4-B5	Air handling unit with rotary heat exchanger, 2458 kg/unit, GOLD RX 070/080 - SILVER C RX 070/080 (Su	721 kg	124471.64	8829.57	61.94	3.16	9.88	138.06	31.85	0.81	97352.42	Aggregat Swegon Gold F RX 14	EPD GOLD RX 070/080 - SILVER C RX 070/080
B6	Electricity, Norway, 2023 (One Click LCA)	6734 kWh	2140591.8	8958.94	30.31	1.34	7.5	78.59	22.55	0.013	10610.06		Country specific electricity mixes based on IEA, OneClickLCA 2025
	Total		2'421'163.7	28'514.4	170.4	6.6	29.1	410.5	93.3	3.7	331'376.3		

APPENDIX E: RENDER OF NATURAL VENTILATION SCENARIO WITH OPAQUE OPENINGS

APPENDIX F: RENDER OF HYBRID VENTILATION SCENARIO WITH LOWERED CEILING (60CM)

APPENDIX G: RENDER OF MECHANICAL VENTILATION SCENARIO WITH LOWERED CEILING (30CM)

APPENDIX H: RENDER OF NATURAL VENTILATION SCENARIO WITH TRANSPARENT OPENINGS

APPENDIX I: RENDER OF HYBRID VENTILATION SCENARIO WITH OPEN CEILING

APPENDIX J: RENDER OF MECHANICAL VENTILATION SCENARIO WITH OPEN CEILING

APPENDIX K: COMFORT SURVEY RESULT (SKANSKA, 2024)

SKANSKA

NAL Frokostmøte Februar 2024

Vertikal Nydelen

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SKANSKA

